

**ONLINE ADVERTISING AND CONSUMERS' PERCEPTION
ON PURCHASE DECISION OF SMARTPHONES**

**SHOFODURIN, ADETAYO OLUWATOSIN
PG/15/0182
B.Sc (LCU)**

**BEING A DISSERTATION SUBMITTED TO THE DEPARTMENT OF
MASS COMMUNICATION VERONICA ADELEKE SCHOOL OF
SOCIAL SCIENCE IN PARTIAL FULFILMENT OF
THE REQUIREMENTS FOR THE AWARD
OF THE DEGREE OF MASTER OF
MASS COMMUNICATION
BABCOCK UNIVERSITY
ILISHAN-REMO
OGUN STATE
NIGERIA**

2017

CERTIFICATION

This dissertation titled, **ONLINE ADVERTISING AND CONSUMERS' PERCEPTION ON PURCHASE DECISION OF SMARTPHONES**, prepared and submitted by **SHOFODURIN ADETAYO OLUWATOSIN (PG/15/0182)** in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of **MASTER OF SCIENCE (Mass Communication)**, is hereby accepted.

Dr. Adekoya, Helen Odunola.
Supervisor

**Accepted as partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of MASTER OF
SCIENCE (Mass Communication)**

**Provost, College of Postgraduate Studies
Prof. Yacob Haliso**

DEDICATION

This dissertation is dedicated to Almighty God.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

God Almighty is highly recognised for the success of this work. This work also owes its existence to the help, support and inspiration of several people. Firstly, I would like to express my sincere appreciation and gratitude to Dr. Adekoya Helen Odunola for her guidance during the course of my research. Her unending support and inspiring suggestions have been precious for the development of this dissertation. In addition, the massive contributions of Professor Akinwande Anjuwon, Dr Ajilore Kolade, Dr Ojomo Olusegun, Dr Akintayo Babafemi, and Dr Akoja Mofoluke towards the progress of this research exercise will never be forgotten. I appreciate the relentless efforts of these hard working lecturers who empowered me with substantial knowledge contributions. I am also indebted to Mr. Ogunwemimo Taiwo and Miss Solo-Anaeto Margaret who were both constant sources of encouragement to me during the course of my Master degree programme here at Babcock University. In addition, Shofodunrin Olufemi, Shofodunrin Olufisayo and Olomojobi Oluwafemi also deserve special thanks as support partners and brothers who solidly stood by me even when I was almost getting discouraged in the data gathering process for this research exercise.

I would also like to thank the kind-hearted officials of Agege local government who attended to me and assisted me in the data gathering process which was very useful for the methodology of this research work. The respondents who were very understanding are being acknowledged here as well because the work would have been incomplete without their immense level of cooperation. Particularly to my parents, Mr Ademola Shofodunrin and Mrs Damilola Shofodunrin, words cannot explain the level of support they invested into this work morally, intellectually and financially.

ABSTRACT

Advertising as a profession and a field of study explains the reason why it cannot be underestimated. However, advertising in the 21st century has gone beyond making use of the traditional sources of the media to create awareness about product services, goods and ideas to prospective consumers. The advent of the new media has solidified the relevance of the internet in advertising. This research exercise examined online advertising and consumers' perception on purchase decision of Smartphones. The study examined the general level of exposure which consumers had towards online advertising. The attention, awareness and perception level of consumers towards Smartphone brands advertised online was being checked as well. The relevance of Gibson's theory of direct perception and the AIDA model was used in backing up the study.

In this study, the descriptive survey research design was adopted making use of the quantitative research method to accurately establish the relationships between the variables considered in the study. Residents of Lagos State from Agege and Ikeja Local Government Areas were the accessible population for this study. The multi-stage sampling technique was used because more than one sampling method was combined in order to arrive at a finite representative sample size for the study. Validated questionnaires were distributed and data was being gathered, analysed and interpreted making use of frequency counts, mean, standard deviation, tables and charts.

This study adopted five objectives and three hypotheses. Eight hundred and sixteen (816) copies of the questionnaire were administered. Majority of the attendants were females and young individuals. It was deduced from this study that pricing, features, brand preferences, social Influence as important factors which contribute to the purchase decision of Smartphones being advertised online. The study also revealed that majority of the respondents pay less attention to online advertisements but are attracted to the graphic quality of advertised contents on social media which is also a form of online advertising. Overall, the study found out that the new media is capable of influencing consumer's choice of purchasing Smartphones being advertised online. This research work made it evident that it becomes mandatory for and strategic for Smartphone manufacturers, vendors and marketers to adopt online advertising through social media.

The purchase of Smartphones, according to the study, depended on the effectiveness of online advertising. It was, therefore, concluded that Smartphone manufacturers, vendors and marketers need to identify online platforms that would enhance user interactivity with the potential for consumer online Smartphone advertisement customized exposure. This study proffered recommendations to Smartphone manufacturers, marketers, and vendors about the appropriate utilization of online advertising for Smartphones; with a view to improving the contents of online adverts of Smartphones as well as making use of the best platform for new media advertising to boost the purchase of Smartphones.

Keywords: Online Advertising, Awareness, Smartphone, Perception, Purchase Decision.

Word Count: 454

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Content	Page
Title page	i
Certification	ii
Dedication	iii
Acknowledgments	iv
Abstract	v
Table of Contents	vi
List of Tables	ix
List of Figures	xi

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1	Background to the Study	1
1.2	Statement of the Problem	4
1.3	Objective of the Study	6
1.4	Research Questions	6
1.5	Hypotheses	6
1.6	Significance of the Study	7
1.7	Scope of the Study	7
1.8	Operational Definition of Terms	8

CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.0	Introduction	9
2.1	Conceptual Model	9
2.2	Review of Relevant Concepts	10
2.2.1	Online Advertising	10

2.2.2	Consumer Perception	14
	Content	Page
2.2.3	Purchase Decision	16
2.2.4	Smartphones	19
2.2.4.1	Smartphone Market	20
2.2.4.2	Consumers' Perception of Smartphones	22
2.2.4.3	Consumers' Purchase of Smartphones	23
2.3	Theoretical Framework	25
2.3.1	Gibson's Theory of Direct Perception	25
2.3.2	AIDA model	26
2.4	Empirical Review	28
2.5	Summary	32

CHAPTER THREE: METHODOLOGY

3.0	Introduction	33
3.1	Research Design	33
3.2	Population	33
3.3	Sampling size and sampling Technique	34
3.4	Research Instrument	42
3.5	Validity of Research Instrument	42
3.6	Reliability of Research Instrument	42
3.7	Administration of Research Instrument	43
3.8	Method of Data Analysis	43

Content	Page
CHAPTER FOUR: DATA ANALYSIS, RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS	
4.0. Introduction	44
4.1 Demographic Characteristics of Respondents	44
4.2 Discussion of Findings	63
CHAPTER FIVE: SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS	
5.1 Summary	70
5.2 Conclusion	71
5.3 Recommendations	72
5.3.1 Smartphone Manufacturers, Marketers and Vendors	72
5.3.2 Online Advertising Platforms for Smartphones	73
5.4 Contribution to Knowledge	73
5.5 Limitation of the Study	74
5.6 Suggestion for Further Studies	75
References	76
Questionnaire	83

LIST OF TABLES

Table	Page
2.1 Online Advertising Formats and Examples	12
2.2 Types of Online Advertising Media	13
3.1 List of Streets in Ward B (Dopemu) at Agege LGA	35
3.2 List of Streets in Ward B (Alade) at Ikeja LGA	37
3.3 List of Streets Systematically Selected in Ward B (Dopemu) at Agege LGA and Distribution of Sample Size	39
3.4 List of Streets Systematically Selected in Ward B (Alade) at Ikeja LGA and Distribution of Sample Size	40
4.1: Demographic Features of Respondents	44
4.2: Awareness of Online Advertisements	46
4.3 Exposure to Smartphone Online Advertising	47
4.4: Attention to Online Advertisements	50
4.5: Consumer Perception of Smartphone	51
4.6: Relationship between Purchase Decision and Perception of Smartphones	53
4.7: Consumer Purchase Decision of Smartphones Advertised Online	54
4.8a Model Summary for the Influence of Email Advertising, Search Engine Advertising, Mobile Advertising and Social Media Advertising on Awareness of Smartphone Brands Advertised Online	55
4.8b Multiple Linear Regression showing the Influence of Email Advertising, Search Engine Advertising, Mobile Advertising and Social Media Advertising on Awareness of Smartphone Brands Advertised Online	55
4.9a Model Summary for the Influence of Attention to Online Advertisements on Perception of Price of Smartphone brands	56
4.9b Simple Linear Regression showing the Influence of Attention to Online Advertisements on Perception of Price of Smartphones Model	57

Table	Page
4.10a Model Summary for the Influence of Attention to Online Advertisements on Perception of Features of Smartphones	57
4.10b Simple Linear Regression showing the Influence of Attention to Online Advertisements on Perception of Features of Smartphones	58
4.11a Model Summary for the Influence of Attention to Online Advertisements on Perception of Quality of Smartphones	59
4.11b Simple Linear Regression showing the Influence of Attention to Online Advertisements on Perception of Quality of Smartphones	59
4.12a Model Summary for the Influence of Attention to Online Advertisements on Perception of Durability of Smartphones	60
4.12b Simple Linear Regression showing the Influence of Attention to Online Advertisements on Perception of Durability of Smartphones	60
4.13a Model Summary for the Influence of Attention to Online Advertisements on Perception of Class of Smartphones	61
4.13b Simple Linear Regression showing the Influence of Attention to Online Advertisements on Perception of Class of Smartphones	61
4.14a Model Summary for the Influence of Consumers' Perception of Price, Features, Quality, Durability and Class of Smartphones on Purchase Decision of Smartphones	62
4.14b Multiple Linear Regression showing the Influence of Attention to Online Advertisements on Perception of Class of Smartphones	62

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure	page
2.1 Framework of Role of Online Advertisements in Consumers' Perception and Purchase Decision of Smartphones,	9
2.2 Funnel Buying Decision Process	16
2.3 Consumer Decision Journey	16
2.4 Consumer Buying Process	18
2.5 AIDA Model	28
4.1 Respondents who Own Smartphones and the Duration of Ownership	45
4.2 Smartphone Brands presently being used	45
4.3 Awareness of Smartphone Brands Advertised Online	49

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

The practice of advertising creates a positive and maximum potential for any manufactured product to be seen as an existing brand being made known to the general public otherwise, such a product will not sell. Advertising is capable of drawing the attention of customers to any kind of product, service and brand and this is done by making use of the media sources to persuade potential consumers or customers to buy the advertised product.

Advertising informs potential customers of an advertised product and it spells out the functions and features of the product. Good advertising is necessary as it creates a demand for the product which is being advertised. Advertising may even create a brand identity for a product or series of products as well as creating an image surrounding a product, so that customers feel that they need it. Advertising can promote a new product and increase sales of existing products. The entire function of advertising is a determinant factor in developing the perception of diverse consumers either in appositive light or in a negative about an advertised product and this in turn determines the final purchase action or purchase decision made by consumers.

Advertising is a non-personal form of communication usually paid for, designed to be persuasive about products, services or ideas by identified sponsors through various media (Belch & Belch, 2004; Dzisah & Ocloo, 2013; Nwankwo, Aboh, Obi, Agu, & Sydney, 2013). According to Balakrishnan & Kumar (2011), advertisements are designed to appeal to different types of audience for the purpose of information dissemination about products and services so as to bring about positive consumer perception and purchase decision. It helps to deliver carefully prepared messages to target audiences thus facilitating marketing programs of the products and services of organizations (Zipporah & Mberia, 2014). The practice of advertising is very important as it helps in building a reputable and positive image about a brand or service in the sight of heterogeneous consumers. Advertising uses various sources of the media in reaching out to the target audience which advertising messages are being designed for. The professional practice of advertising is extended towards the radio, television, newspapers and magazines. Other sources of advertising

include public speaking, door hangers and flyers, event sponsorship and word-of-mouth advertising.

Online advertising is the application of internet capabilities to the process of carefully packaging non-personal communication messages to specific audience in order to engender positive perception and purchase decision of products and services (Tavor, 2011). Online advertising ensures wider coverage because it has a very wide interconnection of individuals, businesses and organizations with huge processing capabilities overcoming geographical boundaries (Ducoffe, 1996). Tavor (2011) observes that the Internet has become a major source of information and has to some extent replaced old media such as the radio, television and the newspaper; this has occurred because the Internet gives the advantage of access to current information and mass dissemination of information. These factors according to Tavor (2011) have jointly contributed to ensuring that over 700 million people world-wide use the internet daily for important activities such as information search and product/service purchase.

In addition, the ubiquity of internet connection has brought about a diversion of companies' and businesses' attention towards the online advertisement platform. Consequently, many companies advertise their products and services online. According to Tavor (2011), online advertising is preferred because it commands a daily audience that is greater than the sum of the entire historical audience of traditional media and it offers interactivity, colorfulness and information currency which ultimately leads to either local or international purchase or products and services.

Kotler (2001) points out that perception involves someone selecting, organizing, and interpreting information and inputs such in order to create a meaningful picture of the world and that each customer perceives the world differently, and perceptions are manifested as attitude. Exposure to advertisements irrespective of the advertising source through which the advertised message is being communicated to consumers has a significant impact in building up the perception of consumers towards an advertised brand. Consumer perception refers to the process by which a consumer selects, organizes, and interprets information and stimuli inputs to create a meaningful picture of the brand or the product (Blank, 2013). Consumer perception is an advertising concept that encompasses a customer's impression, awareness or

consciousness about an advertised brand and products with relevant information about its offerings. Consumer perception is typically affected by advertising, reviews, public relations, social media, personal experiences and other channels

According to Blank (2013), Consumer perception applies the concept of sensory perception to marketing and advertising. Just as sensory perception relates to how humans perceive and process sensory stimuli through their five senses, consumer perception pertains to how individuals form opinions about companies and the merchandise they offer through the purchases they make. Merchants apply consumer perception theory to determine how their customers perceive them. They also use consumer perception theory to develop advertising strategies intended to retain current customers and attract new ones.

Kazmi (2012) posits that consumer usage and buying of any product largely depend upon their perception about the product. The author identified accessibility, availability, and quality, durability regular supply of product and mode of payment as the most important factors that influence consumer perception. Similarly, Wollenberg and Thuong (2014) asserts that brand perception is a term used to describe how consumers experience a particular brand of product; perception can be seen as reality, so brand perception can be seen as real customer's views based on what was promised. Customers' perception helps to increase customers' level of satisfaction which leads to brand loyalty and increases the chance of product repurchase.

McCoy, Everard, Galletta and Polak (2004) found that advertisements on an online platform such as websites could bring about negative or positive perception. This is because it might negatively influence intention to return; however retention of website information was higher when advertisements were in-line or when advertisements were not congruent with website content. However, contrary to expectations, intentions to return were not affected by advertisement placement, while retention of site content was not affected by the existence of advertisements, and intrusiveness of advertisements was not affected by advertisement congruence.

CCS Insight (2014) observes that the global Smartphone market has gone through a high growth rate in recent years, with shipments rising by 40 percent in 2013 which surpassed the 1 billion unit threshold and a forecast of Smartphone shipments of 1.89 billion units by

2018. This development has increased competition in the Smartphone industry to the extent that Apple has redefined their hardware business model while Samsung has scaled its operations; and the barriers to entry have reduced because of the increased adoption of the Android operating system and many design platforms (CCS Insight, 2014). The increased competition among Smartphone manufacturers has brought about a reduction in the market share of notable Smartphone manufacturers. This contributes to the reason why notable Smartphone makers are investing huge in marketing and advertising Smartphone brands via the internet.

Purchase decision is a thoughtful, on-going process that is carried out to ensure eventual satisfaction. Consumers are rational beings and as such apply a systematic process of information utilization for making accurate decisions. This explains why online advertisements of Smartphones become a key factor in either building or collapsing the purchase decision of Smartphone brands by consumers. Purchase decision could also mean meeting target customers' needs and increasing their positive perception (Shareef, Kumar & Kumar 2008). Lay-Yee, Han and Yin-Fah (2013), assert that Smartphone purchase decision is influenced by brand concern, convenience concern, dependency concern, price concern, product feature concern and social influence concern which determine whether advertised Smartphone brands online would be eventually purchased or not. Furthermore Christopher, John and Sudhahar (2014) discover that peer influence affects the purchase decision of Smartphone users when they come across advertised Smartphones online. This study is poised to studying the role of online advertisements on consumers' perception and purchase decision of Smartphones. The purchase decision of various Smartphone brands by prospective consumers in Nigeria would be measured based on the effectiveness of the online advertisement of Smartphones which consumers are exposed to on daily basis thereby strengthening the relevance of this study.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The social significance attached to certain Smartphone brands has qualified Smartphone ownership to be a status making factor. The social influence being driven by Smartphone ownership alongside advertised contents of Smartphones online contributes to the eventual purchase of Smartphones (Kotler & Armstrong, 2010). With the mobile subscriber base pegged at over one hundred million (Nigerian Communications Commission, 2016), Nigeria

seems to be an attractive market for Smartphones. This is evident in the number of different Smartphone brands available in the country. Some of which are Samsung, Apple, Infinx, Techno, Lenovo, Blackberry. The significance of Smartphones for consumers lie the variety of applications present on the Smartphones that allow individuals to perform different activities efficiently (Altena, 2012), even leading to a state of dependency on Smartphones. Thus, Smartphone ownership and the usage of certain Smartphone brands have come to be associated with a level of social status and social significance.

The rapid increase in the number of Nigerians with internet subscription translates to the maximum possibility of an average internet user in Nigeria being exposed to online advertisements of Smartphones which in turn plays a key role in influencing the perception and purchase decision of Smartphones. (Nigerian Communications Commission, 2016) Smartphone marketers continuously invest huge budgets in advertising their brands in order to increase awareness and purchase among consumers. In a bid to maximize visibility for their brands, Smartphone marketers are incorporating online advertising into their strategy (Nielsen 2013). This is in consideration of the fact that more consumers spend time on the internet. Therefore, it becomes imperative to question the return of online advertisements on the investment of Smartphone makers.

Too many advertised messages being displayed at the same time creates a shift in attention by consumers (Miller 2004). This becomes a check to the effectiveness of Smartphone brands advertised online. Consumers' perception is being determined by the contents of smartphone brands advertised online. The developed perception is what determines the eventual outcome of purchase decision by consumers. The high level of investment into advertising by Smartphone manufacturers raises certain questions such as: do consumers pay attention to Smartphone online advertisements? Do the features of Smartphones displayed in Smartphone online advertisements influence consumer perception and purchase decision? Does the budget in online advertising for Smartphone online advertisement reflect positively on consumers' perception and purchase decisions? Thus, this study intends to examine the role of online advertisement on consumers' perception and purchase decision of Smartphones.

1.3 Objective of the Study

The general objective of this study was to examine the role of online advertising in consumers' perception and purchase decision of Smartphones. The specific objectives are:

1. examine consumers' level of exposure to online advertisements;
2. ascertain consumers' awareness level of Smartphone brands advertised online;
3. explore the extent of consumers' attention towards Smartphone online advertisements;
4. explore consumers' perception (price, features, quality, durability, class) of online advertised Smartphones and
5. determine what relationships exist between perception (price, features, quality, durability and class) and purchase decision of online advertised Smartphones.

1.4 Research Questions

1. What is the level of consumers' exposure to online advertising?
2. To what extent are consumers aware of Smartphone brands advertised online?
3. To what extent do consumers pay attention to online advertisements?
4. What is consumers' perception (Price, features, quality, durability, class) of Smartphones?
5. What relationship exists between perception (price, features, quality, durability, class) and purchase decision of Smartphones?

1.5 Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested with 0.05 level of significance:

- H₁: Consumers' exposure to online advertising significantly influences awareness of Smartphone brands advertised online.
- H₂: Attention to online advertisements significantly influences perception (price, features, quality, durability and class) of different Smartphone brands
- H₃: Consumers' perception (price, features, quality, durability and class) of Smartphones significantly influences purchase decision of Smartphones

1.6 Significance of the Study

This study unraveled the impact of online advertisements on consumers' perception and purchase decision of Smartphones. Consumers' awareness about Smartphone brands facilitated by online advertisements either builds up or discourages their perceptions and purchase decision because consumers have access to the metrics that are individually important to them. This study would increase the knowledge of Smartphone makers about the Nigerian market, as it immensely contributed to concretely exposing the current perceptions and purchase decision trends of their products as being viewed by Smartphone consumers. Furthermore, Smartphone manufacturers at the international level now have an insight into features and factors that are most important to majority of the Smartphone users which they may harness in order to develop a comprehensive Smartphone specification plan to suit majority of the Smartphone consumers in Nigeria which may represent the standard that Smartphones may need to meet before they are being allowed to import or manufacture in the country.

Moreover, the relevance of this study centered on assisting advertising practitioners, marketers and Smartphone manufacturers and vendors towards embracing online advertising as this research captured how online advertisements determines the level of consumers' perception and purchase decision of Smartphones.

1.7 Scope of the Study

This study investigated online advertisement on consumers' perception and purchase decision of Smartphones. In the context of this study, Smartphones were not specifically limited to specific brands. This study investigated perception from the perspective of price, features, quality, durability and class, while factors that influence purchase decision was limited to price, features and social influence. This study was conducted among Lagos residents in Ikeja local government and Agege local government, between September and December 2016. In the context of this research work, the category of the respondents that was used for the purpose of this study were individuals ranging from the category of the youths to the adults who were Smartphone users with a considerable level of access and exposure to the Internet, excluding minors.

1.8 Operational Definition of Terms

Online Advertising: This refers to activities carried out on electronic platforms that are powered by the internet and are used to consciously make potential consumers aware of particular brands.

Brand Awareness: This is a process of increasing a consumers' state of information about a brand. It will be measured by developing scales that will require respondents to state their level of awareness of Smartphone brands. In the context of this study, the level of brand awareness by consumers would be determined by the available choices of the smartphone brands which the Smartphone customers are being exposed to via online advertisements.

Purchase Decision: This is an activity carried out by a consumer to take ownership of a Smartphone brand advertised online by Smartphone makers. In the context of this study, consumers' purchase decision of Smartphone brands advertised online will be measured and determined by the extent to which information about advertised smartphones online influence consumers purchase decision.

Perception: This explains the impression which is being created on the mind of various consumers about the quality and features of Smartphone brands they are exposed to via online advertisements. Consumers' perception in the context of this study is the combination of price, features, quality, durability and class. Therefore, perception of consumers towards smart phone brands advertised online will be measured and determined by the extent to which price, features, quality, durability and class affects consumers' perception before an advertised smartphone is being purchased.

Smartphones: They are mobile phones with the functional capability of a computer system with the ability to access the internet and conveniently run downloaded applications.

CHAPTER TWO

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.0 Introduction

This research work starts by illustrating the concepts of interests graphically in a conceptual framework and thereafter reviews the concepts and the selected theories that guide the study.

2.1 Conceptual Model

The concepts that are illustrated in Figure 2.1 are online advertising, consumers' awareness of Smartphone brands, consumers' attention to online advertisements, consumers' perception of Smartphone brands (price, features and social influence) and purchase decision of Smartphone brands.

Figure 2.1 Conceptual Model of Role of Online Advertisements in Consumers' Perception and Purchase Decision of Smartphones

Source: Researcher's Model (2016)

Figure 2.1 indicates that online advertising could lead to consumers' awareness of smart phone brands. In addition, Figure 2.1 shows that consumers' perception in the context of this study is made up of price, features, quality, durability, class and social influence which could directly lead to purchase decision of Smartphones. The conceptual model for this research work makes it visible that online advertisement is a key instrument in influencing the perception and purchase decision of consumers. For every online advertisement seen on the internet, purchase decision and perception about advertised products cannot be possible if the adverts are not capable of attracting the attention of potential Smartphone consumers. In the same vein, this study visibly makes it very evident that the formed perception of consumers about advertised smartphones which they come across online is narrowed down to the price, features, quality, durability and class of the advertised Smartphones which they are being exposed to online. These qualities which make up consumer's formed perception about advertised Smartphones also determines whether consumers will eventually purchase the advertised Smart phones or not.

2.2 Review of Relevant Concepts

This section of the work treats the concepts that have been focused on in this study. The concepts are Online Advertising, Consumer Perception, Purchase Decision, and Smartphone.

2.2.1 Online Advertising

Adekoya (2011) defines online advertising as advertising messages that are available by computer when customers want to receive them. Online advertising according to Papadopoulos (2009) is synonymous with internet advertising and is the delivery of advertising messages and marketing communications through the web. In addition, Tavor (2011) states that online advertising is the application of internet capabilities to the process of carefully packaging non-personal communication messages to specific audience in order to engender positive perception and purchase decision of products and services. Examining these definitions closely indicates that online advertising involves the use of computer based technologies which guarantees interconnectivity and passage of non-personal communication messages to a wide range of people.

Adelabu (2015) identifies the major forms of online advertising as display ads, search-related ads, and online classifieds; Adelabu (2015) further states that the most common form of online advertisements is banners, these are found at the bottom, top, left, right or centre of web pages; the next is pop-up advertisements which are online advertisements that appear suddenly in a new window or in front of the window being viewed. According to Alves (2014), online advertising uses myriad of tools which include search engines. Alves (2014) indicates that many digital communication channels can be adapted for online advertising with each serving diverse communication goals which can range from awareness, engagement, traffic generation, lead generation and sales conversion. Different formats of online advertising most commonly employed today are Search Engine Marketing (SEM), Display Advertisement, Mobile Marketing, Social Media and E-mail Marketing (Alves, 2014).

Heinonen and Rozenveld (2013) argue the potentials of online advertising by making reference to the former CEO of Microsoft, Steve Ballmer who opines that the transformation from offline advertisement to online advertisement would take 10 years. Corroboratively, Lightcap and Peek (2012) indicates that the power of online advertising is epitomised by social media platforms such as Facebook; Lightcap and Peek (2012) argue that Facebook's deployment of action spec targeting, Sponsored Story advertising, and monetization of a growing mobile user base will lead to increased innovation. Online advertising over the next decade will attract a greater migration from traditional advertising such as television and print to online advertising because it is now easier to reach more consumers with Facebook than it is with television (Lightcap & Peek 2012 citing Agrawal, 2012). According to Alves (2014) there are many categorization of online advertising; Alves (2014) indicates that there are ten different formats of online advertising as shown in Table 2.1.

Table 2.1 Online Advertising Formats and Examples

Online Advertising Formats	Examples
Vertical Search	Online yellow pages, job/local and product searches
Display Advertising	Banners ads, like images or video, on websites
E-mail Marketing	Newsletter
Viral Marketing	Any marketing message massive spread by consumers
News Sites	Google Ad Words, AdSense, Yahoo! Publisher Network
Blog Marketing	BlogHer, SocialSpark
Behavioral Advertising	Retarget ads
Social media Marketing	Facebook ads
Contextual Advertising	Specific words on a website have a drink
Affiliate Marketing	Amazon Associates

Source: Alves (2014)

Furthermore, Alves (2014) identifies a different classification format for online advertising along the strategic viewpoint; which considers whether they can be a source of external cost or external revenue for a company; from this perspective, three major groups of online advertising are identified; these are paid, owned and earned. According to Edelman and Salsberg (2010), paid search advertisements are closer to traditional media advertisements, while the owned media correspond to channels that advertisers own, such as corporate websites or Facebook pages. The essence of earned media, on the other hand, is related with leveraging the digital word of mouth, mainly on social media. Notably, Edelman and Salsberg (2010) state that sold and hijacked online advertising should be included in order to account for the growing importance of social media and affiliate networks' marketing communication activities. The relevance of paid media increases with the possibility of better targeting advertisements to consumers through several formats; it is also crucial for enterprises to continue updating their own websites and deliver relevant information by e-mail marketing (Edelman & Salsberg, 2010) (See Table 2.2).

Table 2.2 Types of Online Advertising Media

Types	Definition	Examples
Paid	Whenever a third party media space is bought to promote companies product	Display and Paid Search ads
Owned	When companies use or develop their own channels to advertise	Web sites, Facebook fan pages and email
Earned	If consumers share or create media that was designed by the company	Organic search content share: ratings/review/ranking on community sites
Sold	Other marketers are invited to place content on its owned media	Company sells space on their web site (i.e Google ads Sense and affiliate network)
Hijacked	Those who oppose the company may hostage assets or campaigns	Negative comments on social Media or creation and distribution of their own negative version of an online ad

Source: Edelman and Salsberg (2010)

Marketers should be able to control both paid and owned media; earned media however, allows companies to have publicity at no cost, since these refer to situations where sources external to the company promote it using their own channels; sold media can be seen as new trend, which is still taking its first steps. If a specific website has a huge traffic, some companies might buy media space to place their advertisements, while hijacked media is the opposite of earned media, hackers can either hijack companies' Facebook pages or persuade others to boycott them, this entails putting the brand's or company's reputation at risk (Edelman & Salsberg, 2010)

According to Alves (2014), organic and paid searches are made through search engines, such as Google or Yahoo!, to display keyword search results to web users on search engine results pages (SERPs), and in this way leverage users' search activities for marketing communication purposes. Organic search refers to naturally, or not influenced results generated by web users' searches, the outcomes of this type of search results from applying an algorithm designed by the search provider to users' keyword search. The main objective here is to generate traffic by making sure that the website appears on the top positions of SERP. That is where search engine optimization (SEO), a group of search engine-based techniques used to improve sites' positions on SERP, comes into play there by advertisers may influence organic search through owned media, namely through the optimization of the content, keyword use and linking of their websites, social networked media pages, blogs and

referrals. Every time a user search for specific keywords on the search engine, paid search advertisements are displayed that best match the keywords; however, not all advertisements commissioned are showed, this is because for example Google has an auction bidding system to determine which advertisement appears (Alves, 2014).

According to Alves (2014) social media platforms such as Facebook engage in effective and efficient online advertising by specifically targeting users through their personal features and interests, such as their socio-demographic characteristics, interests, geographical location and online social behaviour. Exploiting online advertising through social media advertising campaigns requires advertisers and agencies to know the size of particular audiences, its growth rate, the amount of traffic being driven by social media to advertisers' websites, and how many leads and sales are being generated from it (Vaughan, 2012).

Todi (2008) identifies a set of criteria that are necessary for online advertising. A successful online advertising should be unobtrusive; this suggests that the usage of pop-up advertisements should be minimized because consumer preferences have shown evolution of tools and methods to stop pop-ups; consequently bringing about the development of non-obtrusive online advertising formats; online advertising needs to be creative in order to attract attention ; furthermore, online advertising has to be interactive; this will enable consumers to engage, display and express their personalities online (Todi, 2008). These suggest that online advertisements that do not put the aforementioned criteria into consideration are set to fail because of the prevailing user preferences in online advertisements' obtrusiveness, creativity and interactivity.

2.2.2 Consumer Perception

Aggrawal (2010) defines perception as how information is collected and categorized; Aggrawal (2010) further notes that perception is influenced by the level of exposure to a stimulus and by one's interpretation. In the same vein, perception is the process by which an individual selects, organises and interprets stimuli into a meaningful and coherent picture of the world (Bednall & Kanuk, 1997). Corroboratively, Schiffman and Kanuk (1997) define perception as the interpretations given to objects or ideas brought one's attention through the senses and how we interpret or give meaning to the world around us and depend on the object and experiences that we encounter in our lives. Nguy (2000), however notes that

perception is a prerequisite of attitudinal development and that an existing attitude plays an important role in the perception of an object.

Aggrawal (2010) states that the study of consumer perception helps firms and organizations to improve their marketing strategies through the strategic understanding of the psychology of how consumers think, feel, reason, and select between different alternatives, the psychology of how the consumer is influenced by his or her environment, the behaviour of consumers while shopping or making other marketing decisions, limitations of consumer knowledge or information processing abilities influencing decisions and marketing outcome, how consumer motivation and decision strategies differ between products that differ in their level of importance or interest that they entail for the consumer; and how marketers can adapt and improve their marketing campaigns and marketing strategies to more effectively reach the consumer.

Randall (2000) notes that brands are perceived as a whole and are not disintegrated mentally into separate entities. James (2005) observes that consumers' perception of a brand quality shows the type of attitude towards the product and predicts the likelihood of purchasing the brand. This suggests that organizations and companies should strive to ensure consumers have a positive attitude towards their products in order to increase the chances of consumers' purchase of such brands. Corroboratively, Baldauf, Cravens, and Binder (2003), posit that perceived quality is positively related to the perceived value of a brand; an increased perceived quality represents the reason consumers choose a product in many purchase scenarios, and some consumers are even willing to pay higher; however, brand loyalty also plays a huge role in influencing the perception of overall value of a brand to a large extent (Beverland (2005).

According to Aggrawal (2010), brand loyalty is the positive consumer perception, however, the psychology underpinning human behaviour tendencies in relation to brand selection is complicated and not easily predictable, therefore, it is important to understand how consumers process, receive/filter information and messages about brand, the necessity to distinguish between spurious, true and brand loyalty based on serendipity. Furthermore, Aggrawal (2010) postulates that brand positioning is essential for creating consumer perception; Aggrawal (2010) states that a strong brand position indicates that a brand has a unique, credible, sustainable, and valued place in the consumer's mind. Consumers'

perception has been presented to be influenced by consumers' socio-cultural contexts. Socio-cultural variables such as patriotism, ethnicity, socio-economic status, family size play significant roles in developing positive perception of the consumers (Aggrawal, 2010). In another instance, because of the prevalence of the socio-economic challenges associated with global warming, Keller (2003) asserts that global warming make consumers use more of eco-friendly products.

According to Dwarika and Gandhi (2007), brand management if correctly carried out could bring about a positive consumer perception because it starts with the conceptualization of a product; which requires teamwork with a perfect marketing plan that aims at a market segment, a market survey is carried out in advance in order to get consumer reactions, while the next stage is the establishment of brand identity in the market by establishing communication lines with the consumers specifically searching for information on how the brand would satisfy them in terms of their needs; this process is then developed with assertive promotions and campaigning using various media and non-media platforms.

2.2.3 Purchase Decision

Court, Mulder and Vetvik (2009) assert that marketers aim to influence users at any stage of their buying decision process in which they might be open to receive and process information about offers, that is, at the so called consumer touch points which have until recently been considered to be linear and sequential and inseparable from each other as depicted in Figure 2.2.

Figure 2.2: Funnel Buying Decision Process

Source: Court et al. (2009)

Court, Mulder and Vetvik (2009) argues that the information explosion through the globalization of the Internet and digital media have empowered consumers, thereby leading to exponential multiplicity of touch points; while buying decisions processes themselves have become highly iterative, rather than sequential, in what has been termed the consumer

decision journey(see Figure 2.3). The circular decision making processes necessarily implies a relationship between decision stages.

Figure 2.3: Consumer Decision Journey

Source: Court et al. (2009)

Aggrawal (2010) states that consumer buying decision process is the process undertaken by consumer in regard to a potential market transaction before, during and after the purchase of a product or service. Consumer decision making process generally involves five stages which are problem recognition, which is a purchase decision making process that begins when a buyer becomes aware of an unsatisfied need or problem; it is an important stage in buying decision process, because without recognizing the need or want, an individual would not seek to buy goods or service. In addition, Aggrawal (2010) and Boadu (2012) state that the next stage of consumer buying decision process is information search which comes to play after the consumer has recognized a need, such a costumer will make effort to find information to solve the need. Alternatives evaluation occurs when consumers evaluate criteria referring to various dimensions; features, characteristics and benefits that a consumer desires in order to solve a certain problem; here, it is the product's features and its benefit that influence consumer to prefer a brand; the consumer will decide which product to buy from a set of alternative products factoring brand's unique features/benefit that will be derived (Aggrawal, 2010; Boadu, 2012). The next stage is purchase action which involves selection of brand and the retail outlet to purchase such a product from; at this stage, the consumers prefers a nearby retail outlet for minor shopping and they can willingly go to a faraway store when they purchase items which are of higher values and which involve

higher sensitive purchase decision; the last stage is post-purchase actions; consumer's favourable post-purchase evaluation influences consumers' satisfaction (Aggrawal, 2010; Boadu, 2012).

Figure 2.4: Consumer Buying Process

Source: Kotler (2000)

Aggrawal (2010) indicates that social factors refer to forces that other people exert and which affect consumers' purchase decision; these include culture/subculture, social class and reference groups. Psychological Factors also influence purchase decision, they are internal to consumers and generate forces that influence consumers' purchase decisions; these can include motives, perception, learning, attitude and personality; in addition, personal factors include things that are unique to a consumer and influence purchase decision; they include demographic factors, lifestyle, and situational factors (Aggrawal, 2010; Kotler, 2000). Macdonald and Sharp (2000) postulate that brand awareness has the ability to make a customer recognize and recall a brand in a giving situation and subsequently influence purchase decision, when consumers want to buy a product, and a brand name comes to their minds at once, it shows that product has higher brand awareness (Boadu, 2012).

Corroboratively, Blackwell, Miniard, and Engel (2001) assert that it is important for customers to reach an awareness level of brands in order to increase the likelihood of making a positive purchase decision; this is because the product needs to be in the set of awareness before the consideration stage is being reached; It is believed that brands with a higher level of recognition would be more likely purchased than the ones with no recognition. According to Shimp (2010), there are four levels of brand awareness; the first level is brand unawareness, where customers do not recognize the brand and have no initial interest in the brand; the second level is brand recognition, this is when a customer is able to identify a brand without hints; the third level is brand recall which indicates a deeper level of brand awareness it is often the goal of marketers. Lastly, the fourth level is top of mind, this is the stage in which company's brand is the first brand that consumers recall.

DeLong, Bao, Wu, Chao, and Li (2004) posit that purchase decision is influenced by customers' knowledge about a brand the brand image, this positions marketers to constructing the ideal brand that enhances the brands' purchase. Brand image is consequently constructed through advertising, word of mouth, reference groups, celebrities, and media Mihalcea & Catoiu (2014). Furthermore, Muniz and O'Guinn (2001) state that creating a specific meaning of the brand through media, celebrities and reference groups encourage customers to deem themselves as a part of the same cultural environment as well as a certain social group thereby influencing purchase decision. Customers' purchase decision could be described by different purchasing approaches, different customers have separate understanding of what constitutes purchase; purchase decisions are informed by consumers' developmental patterns ranging from childhood to adulthood; purchase decision is also affected by customer consumption values, the consumption values explain why a customer chooses one brand over another, and the type of product that is more suitable and adaptable for consumers; purchase decision also depends on consumer approach to the product and what consumption values he or she possesses (Petrauskaite, 2014).

2.2.4 Smartphones

According to Khanuja (2013), a smartphone is a mobile phone that is built on mobile operating system with an advanced computing capability and connectivity than an ordinary mobile phone. In the same vein, Shin, Lee, and Odom (2014) define smartphone as a combination of the cellular phone and the personal computer. Khanuja (2013) indicates that

the first smartphone that integrated these capabilities was known as the personal digital assistant (PDA) with mobile phone features; later models included the functionality of media players, digital cameras, video cameras and GPS navigation system to form one multi-tasking gadget. Nowadays, smartphones also include high resolution camera with touch screen, web browser, high speed data processing functionality, WiFi, mobile broadband backed by rapid of development of mobile applications which drive smartphone adoption (Khanuja, 2013). Corroboratively, Jordão (2010) asserts that the introduction of smartphones brought about the seamless integration of business and entertainment which was aimed at satisfying the huge demand for data exchange through ubiquitous, fast, wireless access devices. On the other hand, Vikström and Zheng (2013) view basic phones as devices that have no touch screen or internet connectivity and the usage is mainly phone calls and text messaging; feature phones are mobile devices that have varying support for touch screens, Wi-Fi, web browser and limited third party applications.; while smartphones are devices that have multi-touch screens with full browser/HTML support, Wi-Fi, 3G/4G, GPS, accelerometer and an extensive range of third party applications available from an in-phone store.

Nagarkoti (2009) describes a Smartphone as a mobile phone, generally built with a mobile operating system that has more advance computing capability and connectivity than a feature phone. Smartphones now have high resolution big touch screens and web browsers that can display standard web pages with mobile optimized pages; a smartphone allows users to download and install third-party applications from application store; these are a collection of applications related users needs in terms of internet browsing, email, navigation, social media, music, news, games, finance, health and fitness, notes, calendar, weather forecast and so on; smartphones are developed with an operating system that allows installing applications; examples are Apple's IOS, Microsoft's Windows, Google's Android and Nokia's Symbian (Nagarkoti, 2009).

2.2.4.1 Smartphone Market

Soo (2015) indicates that mobile device market trend before the Smartphone era was dominated by Nokia brand for over 10 years through the adoption of cost effective strategy and efficient distribution channel structure all around the world, Nokia sold many cell phones ranging from high-end to low-end cell phones in large volumes. The advent of

Smartphones in 2009 however brought about diverse changes to the mobile phone market; Smartphones such as the Nokia Symbian or Blackberry had existed in the mobile phone market but the iPhone was the first device with an easy and diversified applications and ecosystem; Apple provided the hardware, operating system and diversified applications; consumers could utilize their mobile phones as personal computers with various applications such as the Safari web browser, E-mail, and navigations; this was notably made possible by Apple's development of a digital platform to distribute mobile applications on iOS, allowing third parties to develop applications; Apple gave access to the App Store in July, 2008, and now has more than 1,400,000 applications in the app store (Soo, 2015). Apple through careful brand awareness and strategic branding has recorded tremendous sales and profits every year; in 2011, Samsung overtook Nokia in the mobile devices market, since then, feature phone sales have decreased rapidly while Smartphone sales started to increase at a rapid pace; the traditional champions (Nokia, LG and Motorola), were stuck in the existing product portfolio, while losing sales and shares except for Apple and Samsung who expanded the Smartphone portfolios (Soo, 2015).

The International Data Corporation (IDC) (2016) indicates that Smartphone vendors shipped a total of 343.3 million Smartphones worldwide in the second quarter of 2016 (2Q16). This was relatively flat, up 0.3% from 2Q15 when vendors shipped 342.4 million units; the market showed greater sequential growth as shipments were up 3.1% from 333.1 million in the first quarter of 2016; while Apple is now putting more emphasis on 'Device as a Service' to try to prevent lengthening replacement cycles in order to increase sales. Additionally, the overall China market slowdown continues to increase competition in other high growth markets such as India, Indonesia, and Middle East; findings show that low-end Chinese Smartphones are having success penetrating non-China markets, despite low-end competition from local brands already in place (International Data Corporation, 2016).

Samsung remains the Smartphone brand with the highest shipment which was achieved because of the launch of the well accepted Galaxy S7 and S7 Edge brands. Apple's second quarter 2016 is seasonally its lowest of the year as consumers purchase have reduced in anticipation of the next big launch in the third quarter; Apple shipped 40.4 million units in 2Q16, which marked the lowest quarterly volume in seven quarters, despite the mid-cycle introduction of the iPhone SE; in the face of declining shipments, Apple has witnessed

strong sales from established and emerging markets because of the launch of the more affordable iPhone SE brand; as Smartphone prices continue to drop and competition increases at the high-end portfolio, Smartphone manufacturers need to continue to make 'flagship-type' devices at affordable prices in order to encourage upgrading on a more frequent basis (International Data Corporation, 2016). It is important to note however that Chinese brands such as Huawei, OPPO, vivo, and Xiaomi have witnessed success with this strategy by shipping premium styled devices that focus on the features that matter most to consumers, such as imaging, sound quality, and design (International Data Corporation, 2016)

According to Soo (2015), the advent of Chinese Smartphone makers into the Smartphone market was possible after the Chinese government removed the policy of the approbation for mobile phone manufacturing, this led to small-sized vendors imitating well known Smartphone brands such as iPhone; these manufacturers provided unique functions such as mobile TV or dual SIM mode; according to a research conducted by iSuppli cited in Soo (2015), such Smartphone makers sold 145 million units in 2009, which accounted for 35% of market share in China; this influenced the big IT companies and OEM vendors in China to start paying attention to the Smartphone market and entered the market in 2011; Huawei and ZTE are global telecommunications equipment manufacturers, and Lenovo is a global PC maker; Hisense and TCL are LCD TV production companies in China; they had already built competitive technology related with the IT and communication fields (Soo, 2015). In addition, OEM manufacturers such as Tyenwi, Gionee and OPPO have grown their manufacturing capacity and experience; they had enough technology to provide quad-core devices with high R&D investment because of their experience as global suppliers of communication equipment; notably, weak brand awareness in the global market made it difficult for them to gain customers in the developed countries (Soo, 2015).

2.2.4.2 Consumers' Perception of Smartphones

Khanuja (2013) identifies the importance of giving credence to analyzing consumers' perception of durable Smartphone brands. Khanuja (2013) states that locally produced Smartphones and foreign brand choice influence consumers' perception of brand image, brand awareness and brand quality. Globalization has brought about ubiquity of information thereby ensuring that consumers have access to more information on Smartphone brands

regarding durability, price, and quality. Consumers however prefer lower-range Smartphone brands because of lower price tags; however, consumers that want Smartphones with better quality, durability with a higher perception of status enhancement prefer foreign brands such as Apple Smartphones; this is why Smartphone companies spend a lot of money on advertising in order to influence customers' perception for profitable consumer behaviour (Khanuja, 2013). Furthermore, Dziri (2011) observes that most of the Smartphone parts are produced by sub-market oligopolies while with few specialize in direct competition with each other; this is typified by a situation where Smartphone manufacturers are investing increasingly in order to promote their platforms ahead of others and thus differentiate themselves through consumers' perception.

According to Soo (2015) the iPhone accomplishment into being a flagship Smartphone manufacturer with a dominating position in the market took only 7 years after Steve Jobs announced the first iPhone in 2007. At the same time, Nokia, Motorola, and LG that were feature phone central firms whose fortunes fell sharply. Nokia failed to transit to a successful smartphone OS (Operating System) in the global market after the iPhone came out. Apple brought out a new form of competition, based on software (operating system) as well as hardware (devices); the two prominent OSs, Android and iOS, expanded market share drastically whereas Symbian that was almost the only smartphone OS before shrunk. Nokia stuck to the Symbian OS that was perceived by consumers to be less convenient and innovative than iOS or Android. In 2011, Samsung overtook Nokia in the mobile devices market; thereby leading to the decline in demand and manufacture of feature phones while Smartphone sales started to increase at a rapid pace from 2011 (Soo, 2015). The initial champions of the mobile market (Nokia, LG and Motorola) were stuck with their product portfolio thereby lost sales and shares because they failed to quickly notice and react to the changing consumers' perception which favoured Apple and Samsung who started to expand their Smartphone portfolios because of an improved customer perception of their brands.

2.2.4.3 Consumers' Purchase of Smartphones

According to the International Data Corporation (2016), Samsung remains the leader in the worldwide Smartphone market as a result of the consumer demand and purchase of the new Galaxy S7 and Galaxy S7 Edge flagship handsets. The new models were perceived to be the

right combination of style and features which helped Samsung grow profits. Furthermore, the inclusion of removable storage, waterproofing, and faster processor increased consumers' perception of the Samsung brand which led many consumers to purchase the new models; besides this, the J-Series is performing well in both developed and emerging markets because of the introduction of new models such as the J7, J5 and J3, which offer different features for different categories of users at various sizes and prices. Samsung is followed closely by Apple; Apple's second quarter sales in 2016 saw a 15% decline from the 47.5 million units shipped in 2015. The new 4-inch iPhone SE has although proved successful in both emerging and developed markets by capturing many first-time Smartphone buyers as well as Android users switching over to the Apple ecosystem. The success of the cheaper SE did, however, have an impact on the overall average selling price (ASP) for an iPhone in the quarter. The ASP for an iPhone was \$595, down 10.1% from \$662 one year ago (International Data Corporation, 2016).

The third ranked most purchased Smartphone brand in the second quarter 2016 is Huawei; it sold most of its Smartphones in the domestic and European markets. The increase in these two regions contributed to shipments totaling 32.1 million units, up 8.4% from last year. Huawei's premium lineup of phones, such as the new P9 and Mate 8 handsets, also pushed 25% of the quarter's volume to the high-end with prices ranging from \$500-\$600. The Honor Series also combined with the Y-Series balanced out the mid-range and low-end with models such as the Honor 5X and V8 proving successful as premium affordable alternatives; With Huawei being the number one flagship premium Smartphone manufacturer in China at the moment, Huawei's remaining challenge will once again be penetrating the U.S. market at the high-end to compete with both Samsung and Apple (International Data Corporation, 2016).

Furthermore, the fourth ranked most purchase Smartphone brand is OPPO which is a popular Smartphone brand in China. It maintained its aggressive marketing and advertising in second quarter of 2016, especially for its flagship R9 Smartphone device, which has helped it to increase sales in the quarter. It continued to leverage its dominance in Tier 3 to Tier 5 cities in China, which has significantly contributed to the strong growth. In Tier 1 cities, OPPO continued to be a leading sponsor for big name entertainment shows which has helped build the brand and bring light to its high-end portfolio. The key model for OPPO is

forecasted to be the R9, which right now is its top shipping model and the aggressive marketing around the device shows the company's ambition in the high end of the market. Overall growth is still primarily in lower-tier China cities, as well as other big opportunity emerging markets such as India and Indonesia (International Data Corporation, 2016). Lastly vivo is the fifth most purchased Smartphone brand in the second quarter of 2016. It is on an upward trajectory in China, with momentum spread across multiple product models; presently, vivo is still 100% focused on Asia/Pacific region, with the majority of volume sales still in China; vivo had several new product launches in China during the second quarter of 2016; they include the V3 and V3 Max, it also successfully adopted celebrity endorsement in order to improve consumer perception and awareness of their brand, this has improved the sales of the brand (International Data Corporation, 2016).

2.3 Theoretical Framework

This section discusses the theory and model that forms the foundation for this study. These are Gibson's theory of direct perception and AIDA model.

2.3.1 Gibson's Theory of Direct Perception

This theory was developed by J. J. Gibson with the belief that human cognitive apparatus was created and formed by a long evolutionary influence of external environment which is apparent in its structure and abilities (Démuth, 2013). The theory was developed with the presumptions that humans learn to extract only the information which is necessary for our survival which is in consonance with Darwin's theory of evolution; Gibson arrived to a conclusion that by detailed analysis of data collected from the environment, humans may acquire all the essential information about objects by direct perception of their perceivable qualities and this is not only information about their size or structure, but also about their importance and potential application.

Gibson states that it is possible to perceive, using senses, the potential use of particular objects the same way as it is possible to perceive the structure of these objects. Affordance is the quality of an object or it is the thing we might be able to do with this object. Gibson was convinced that if we take a look at a ladder we might also see the possibility to climb up or down; similarly, we can see the use of a hammer for driving nails or the possibility that a certain object can be thrown or vice versa that it might have an aesthetic function only. This

can be applied to all common activities we do with objects, but also to atypical, original or highly abstract ways of use. The core of Gibson's concept is a conviction that our perception is based on information volume of sensory inputs, which we further process only via revealing and explaining the available information. Therefore, from the point of view of processing information it is not necessary to operate with images of sensory representations or with some mental objects (Démuth, 2013).

This theory is relevant to this study because it explains how online advertisements of Smartphones serves as stimulus from which consumers get appropriate information that is used for Smartphone purchase decision. From the assumption of this theory, it is evident that the external influence on the cognitive structure of consumers is highly dependent on advertisements they come across on the Internet which determines their perception level and purchase decision of Smartphones. However, information gathered on the internet about Smartphones goes beyond just forming up the perception of Smartphone users towards purchasing a Smartphone but creates an atmosphere where Smartphone users have a full knowledge about the price, features, quality, durability and class of the exact type of Smartphone they intend to purchase. The core of Gibson's concept as regards this theory serving as a conviction that our perception is based on information volume of sensory inputs, which we further process only via revealing and explaining the available information explains the relevance of the internet towards providing Smartphone users with both an audio and a visual advantage which directly or indirectly affects their cognitive mindset and sensory input with retentive messages about the physical features and major relevance of the category or brand of Smartphone brand or brands which they intend to purchase.

2.3.2 AIDA Model

AIDA model was created by E.S Lewis in 1900. It is a behavioural model with the purpose to make sure that an advertisement raises Awareness, stimulate Interest, and leads the customer to Desire and eventually Action (Hackley, 2005). The model is highly persuasive and it is said to often unconsciously affect our thinking (Butterfield, 1997). With the AIDA model, Strong suggested that for an advertisement to be effective it has to be one that commands Attention, leads to Interest in the product and thence the Desire to own and use the product and then finally leads to Action. For an advertisement to be considered successful, it has to be designed in such a way that the customers pass through all these four

phases, with all being equally important. The model implies that advertising should inject memorable and believable messages that will spur customers to act in a certain way (Brierley, 2002).

In 1898, Lewis introduced the hierarchy of effects for the first time along with three steps: attention, interest and desire. A theoretical framework was developed by Strong (1925), where he described how business had to attract attention, maintain interest and create desire (AID) in order to be a market leader. After sometime, Lewis added another step “purchase action” and AIDA model came into existence. This model is still one of the most referred to models in the advertising and personal selling literature (Barry, 1987). The advertisement must receive attention, having attention it must create interest, having the readers’ interest it must create desire to buy; having created the desire to buy it should help decision (Macey, 1900). Purchasing process starts with rising wants and ends with purchase action. In the author’s work, he made reference to the fact that sellers were using different theories to influence people so he finally developed a theory to explain the customers purchase process: “Attention, Interest, Desire, Action, and Satisfaction” but he omitted the last element from his theory and finally the model is known as AIDA model. A, I, D, A which refers to Attention, Interest, Desire and Action respectively is an acronym used in marketing and advertising that describes a common list of events that may occur when a consumer engages with an advertisement. Below are brief explanations about the AIDA model.

A – Attention (Awareness): attract the attention of the customer.

I – Interest: raises customer interest by focusing on and demonstrating advantages and benefits (instead of focusing on features, as in traditional advertising).

D – Desire: convince customers that they want and desire the product or service and that it will satisfy their needs.

A – Action: lead customers towards taking action and purchasing.

Based on the assumption of AIDA model, the aim of advertising is to attract the attention from potential clients, arouse their interest and desire to the final buying action.

According to the AIDA model, getting Attention, raising Interest, building Desire and putting it in Action are the four steps or elements that an advertisement should have to

persuade consumers and meet marketing objectives. The model shows the cognitive phases of a consumer purchasing something from grabbing attention to getting them hooked and then compelling them to take actions on it by creating conviction. The first stage of the model (Attention) is centered on the cognitive mindset of consumers after being exposed to an advertisement. The second and third phase of the model (Interest and Desire) plays a major role in developing the affective mindset of consumers while the last phase of the model (Action) is the behavioural stage which finally determines the eventual action to be carried out by consumers.

Figure 2.5: AIDA Model

Source: Businesstopia (2016)

The relevance of AIDA model to this study is reflective due to the reason that before Smartphone users develop a perception about a Smartphone brand, the four stages of the explained model must be passed through and the relevance of these model serve as a pillar of support to consumers' perception of advertised Smartphone brands seen online. The developed perception would actualize consumers' action to eventually purchase advertised Smartphones seen via online advertisements. It is also clear that the cognitive mindset of consumers must be addressed before they can be persuaded by online advertisements of Smartphones to influence their purchase decision.

2.4 Empirical Review

Malviya, Saluja and Thakur (2013), in their study on factors influencing consumer's purchase decision towards Smartphones in Indore located in India, confirmed the significance of pricing, features, brand preferences, social Influence as important factors which contribute to the purchase decision of Smartphones being advertised online. Social influence acts for the brands used by the people as a status symbol, specifically for Apple

and Samsung products. Furthermore, features have always been very important, as they form the product specifications and the consumers pay high attention towards the features of a Smartphone being advertised online. This is because the Smartphone is needed to conduct several tasks such as browsing internet, handling documents, connecting to social networks etc., all of which strengthens a consumer's purchase decision of a Smartphone. Features of a Smartphone are also considered by a Consumer, as an important reason to purchase a Smartphone. On the other hand, features differ from brand to brand, Thus, features also act as differentiation factors in Brand Preferences; other factors such as configuration, storage space, WI-Fi, GPS, Touchscreen, High- Resolution Camera, applications are found to be considered highly important by consumers while searching for features of a Smartphone when they go through the details of Smartphones advertised online which in turn forms up their perception. Furthermore, the Smartphone Operating System also had a fairly good impact on the Brand Preference, making a weak but worth enough variables to be considered while establishing Brand differentiation (Malviya et al., 2013).

In addition, Malviya et al. (2013) discovered that Smartphone manufacturers should focus on durability, which was perceived by consumers mostly in Apple's iPhones, but not in other brands, it was therefore suggested that other Smartphone makers such as Samsung, Sony and HTC need increase the consumers' perception of durability by including it among the advertised features online. Another Other factors are battery life, which is perceived better in Nokia Smartphones. Apple was found not to be popular among higher age-groups, while Samsung and Blackberry had a consistent segment with Samsung being the most desired brands; gender showed no significant difference when it came to the most preferred Smartphone brand. However, Apple, Samsung, HTC, and Blackberry are the most desired brands; more than half of the consumers were users of Apple, Samsung, Sony and Blackberry and want to retain their current brands as their future brands (Malviya et al., 2013).The findings dwelt on the fact that the purchase decision and perception of consumers are being influenced by the advertised features and characteristics of Smartphones being displayed online. It was however concluded that certain brands should adapt the measure of giving detailed information about the specifications of their phones being advertised online in order to positively influence consumer choice.

Nagarkoti (2009), in a study in India, divided study participants into two groups for a focus group discussion. All the participants in a study had expensive Smartphones, which were perceived to be more durable, reliable, have higher processing ability, large selection of applications, better hardware and multifunction ability. Social factors had no effect on purchase decision of consumers. The study suggested that Smartphones are essential products and they are not luxury products (Nagarkoti, 2009). Consumers' purchase decisions were influenced by one or more personal factors such as marital status and age, as consumers who are unmarried and young tended to purchase more expensive Smartphones because of reduced financial responsibilities. Economic circumstance is also another factor that influences consumers' purchase decision of Smartphones. Other factors that influence consumers' purchase decisions are personality and self-concept, lifestyle and occupation (Nagarkoti, 2009).

In addition, Smartphone users mostly use their Smartphones for updating social media platforms (facebook, twitter, viber, skype, Whatsapp), phone calls, text messages, weather forecast, news reading, travel planner, online shopping, flight booking, playing games, online banking, online postal services, playing videos, listening to songs, managing everyday finance, making schedules, internet browsing, emails, health and fitness, calendar, checking time, alarm clock, programming purposes, navigation, taking pictures, calculator and checking sports information; Smartphones are used between 10 to 20 times a day, the average time on Smartphones range between 2-3 hours per day; while the minimum hour is 1 hour and maximum 5-6 hours per day (Nagarkoti, 2009). Relating this empirical finding to the context of this study, it is evident the built perception of consumers about an advertised Smartphone in terms of its price, features, durability and class determines the developed choice of consumers when they come across Smartphone advertisements online. Also, the functional features of the advertised brand of Smartphones determines the eventual purchase of the advertised brand as consumers tend to be concerned about features before purchasing.

Kumar (2011), in his empirical study using standard and mean deviation online advertising was examined alongside consumer behavior with special emphasis and reference being made to Nestle Limited in India. It was discovered that Online advertising and sales promotion together with the image of a company influences the buying decision of a consumer. In the study, the finding also gathered that the quality and the price of a product

are influential factors in determining if a consumer would purchase a brand product or not. Within the context of this study, it is evident that the physical features as well as the advertised characteristics of Smartphone brands advertised online will go a long way in building up the perception and the purchase decision of Smartphone consumers.

In another research carried out by Wang (2011) titled Online Shopper Decision, it was discovered that in China when consumers want to buy, they first look at the brand and the characteristics of the product they intend purchasing or the service they intend patronizing. They equally want to be sure about the credibility source of the Online advertising medium they are exposed to as well as the features of what is being advertised which in turn plays a major role in building up a consumer's willingness to purchase the advertised brand or product seen on the internet. Therefore, in relating this particular empirical study to the research work, it is evident that the attention and exposure of consumers towards online advertising determines the level of their perception and purchase decision of Smartphone brand they see online. The brand name and features of the advertised brand is also an important factor which determines the eventual purchase of that product.

Kantar world panel which is a global expert in shoppers' behavior empirically reviewed in 2014 that globally, although consumers are familiar with the term Smartphone, they still perform a lot of findings before purchasing their device; only 30% do not conduct any research before buying a Smartphone, while 70% who conducted research prior to buying, recommendation and advice from people influenced them mostly. Furthermore, Kantar world panel (2014) asserts that the availability of working models and a good promotion are the two things that consumers recall the most from their in-store experience with Smartphones. In addition, 59% of buyers who were recommended a Samsung phone went ahead and bought one while the rest opted for other Smartphones in the Android ecosystem; while only 6% of consumers who were recommended Samsung purchased an iPhone, value has the strongest influence. Consumers are still motivated by specific Smartphone functionalities which might be due to the fact that design has become standardized that consumers put functionality over design; screen size is the most important design driver for consumer, yet while 42% of consumers are motivated by screen size, only 30% are motivated by quality and resolution of the screen which suggests that screen size attracts consumers more than quality (Kantar world panel, 2014). This reveals that the

functionalities of advertised Smartphones online is a key factor in building up the perception of consumers thereby causing them to eventually purchase the advertised Smartphone brand.

Osman, Talib, Sanusi, Yen and Alwi (2012) carried out a study in Malaysia and it was discovered that the feature that consumers prefer most is to connect to Internet through Wi-Fi (62%) than 3G (38%); consumers indicate that the trend in community influences them during Smartphone purchasing decision. Consumers also consider needs for the Smartphone, software preferences, cost of plan, and hardware; while signal reception is the weakest determinant Smartphone purchase. In addition, the study revealed that Smartphone design is the most common specification that consumers consider when buying a Smartphone, because it is the most visible feature and representing the first impression to the consumers, this is followed by price, computing power are considered during Smartphone purchase decision (Osman et al., 2012).

Wollenberg and Thuong (2014) in a study carried out about consumer behavior in the Smartphone market in Vietnam found that advertising has slight impact on brand perception in Smartphone, perceived quality also influences respondents' brand perception, price factor has a significant influence on brand perception, advertising partially influences consumers buying decision, perceived quality significantly influences consumer purchasing decision in Smartphone market while price factor has a strong impact on customer purchase decision of Smartphones. Advertising was also recognized as a positive factor in pushing Smartphone brands. A questionnaire was designed to measure the opinion of Smartphone consumers that relate to brand perception and consumer purchase decision. The study showed that advertising, perceived quality, brand perception, price as well as word of mouth is capable of an advertised product being purchased by consumers.

2.5 Summary

This chapter illustrates the conceptual framework and establishes the connections which exist between the theories and models in line with the variables in the study. The chapter reviews relevant literature on online advertising, consumer perception and consumer purchase decision. The study adopts Gibson's theory of direct perception and AIDA model to explain the role of online advertisements on consumer perception and purchase decision of Smartphones.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.0 Introduction

This chapter consists of the research design, the processes, tools that were adopted for the study. The study detailed the direction of this study by focusing on research design, population, sampling techniques, sample and instrument for data collection.

3.1 Research Design

Research design is a complete plan for the generation of evidences that are suited both to a certain set of criteria and to the research question raised by the researcher (Bryman & Bell 2007). It is also known as a proposal to carry out a study, which involves strategies of inquisition and methods of data analysis (Creswell, 2009). In this study, the descriptive survey research design was adopted. This is because the study sought to inquire about a phenomenon from a cross-section of a population. In addition, the quantitative research method examined the relationship among variables it was therefore deemed appropriate for this study in order to accurately establish the relationships between the variables considered in the study.

3.2 Population

Residents of Lagos State were the accessible population for this study. Lagos State has the largest economy and the largest collection of internally generated revenue in Nigeria. Lagos state which is a cosmopolitan city is the commercial nerve of Nigeria where Internet related jobs are rampant. More so, majority of the available private Internet service providers in Nigeria have their headquarters based in Lagos and this is a cogent reason most businesses are Internet driven in Lagos. The target population for this study was Lagos state residents within Agege local government and Ikeja local government area of Lagos state. This is due to the fact that Ikeja local government area is the IT hub of Lagos state with a high level of internet related commercial activities there in. On the other hand, Agege local government is populated with youths who have a considerable level of exposure to the internet and are smartphone users. According to the 2006 Census, Lagos State has 20 Local Government

Areas and has 9,113,605 people with a land mass of 3,496.45 klm². In the context of this research work, the category of the respondents that were considered for the purpose of this study were individuals ranging from the category of youths to adults who were Smartphone users with a considerable level of access to the Internet excluding infants and children. However, in the context of this study, youths and adults were seen as those within the age range of 15 years of age to 51 years of age and above.

3.3 Sample size and sampling Technique

The sample size for this study was 814 residents of Agege local government area and Ikeja local government area in Lagos state. The sample size was derived using a formula developed by Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2009). This formula takes 5% error of margin into consideration. The derivation of the sample size is explained below:

According to the 2006 Census, the population of the **Agege LGA** is 461,743, the next step is to calculate the minimum sample size of the population as suggested by Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2009) by using the following formula

$$n = p\% \times q\% \times \left[\frac{z}{e\%} \right]^2$$

n is the minimum sample size required

$p\%$ is the proportion belonging to the specified category

$q\%$ is the proportion not belonging to the specified category

z is the z value corresponding to the level of confidence required

$e\%$ is the margin of error required.

Therefore:

$$n = 50 \times 50 \times \left(\frac{1.96}{5\%} \right)^2$$

$n = 384.16$ **approximately 384** is the minimum sample size for this study. **Calculating adjusted sample size** requires substituting **384** in the following formula

$$n = n/1 + (n/\text{population})$$

$$n = \frac{n}{1 + \left(\frac{n}{\text{Population}}\right)}$$

Therefore:

$$n = \frac{384}{1 + \left(\frac{384}{461,743}\right)}$$

Therefore the adjusted sample size is 383.7, approximately 384.

Finally, **calculating the sample size adjusted by response rate**

Substitute **384** for ***n*** and **95** for ***re%*** in the following formula

$$n^a = \frac{n \times 100}{re\%}$$

Therefore, $n^a = \frac{384 \times 100}{95} = 408.25$

95

The sample size for Agege LGA is 404 respondents.

Table 3.3 List of Streets Systematically Selected in Ward B (Dopemu) at Agege LGA and Distribution of Sample Size

Adegbola Street	First 25 houses X 2 respondents = 50 respondents+ 1 respondent = 51 respondents
Akinwunmi Street	First 25 houses X 2 respondents = 50 respondents+ 1 respondent = 51 respondents
Buluro Street	First 25 houses X 2 respondents = 50 respondents+ 1 respondent = 51 respondents
Ogunjobi Street	First 25 houses X 2 respondents = 50 respondents+ 1 respondent = 51 respondents
Olorunlogbon Street	First 25 houses X 2 respondents = 50 respondents+ 1 respondent = 51 respondents
Salako Street, Subuola Street	First 25 houses X 2 respondents = 50 respondents+ 1 respondent = 51 respondents
Subuola Street	First 25 houses X 2 respondents = 50 respondents+ 1 respondent = 51 respondents
Union Road (New)	First 25 houses X 2 respondents = 50 respondents+ 1 respondent = 51 respondents
Total	408 respondents

Table 3.3 indicates the distribution of the sample size across the systematically selected streets at Ward B (Dopemu) at Agege LGA. To get the respondents, the first twenty five (25) houses on each of the selected street were systematically selected (with house numbers) in order to eliminate bias. From which the first house, three (3) respondents was selected while the rest of the twenty four houses on each street, 2 respondents each were selected totaling four hundred and eight (408) respondents. However, in a situation where approached respondents were not internet users or Smartphone owners as the case may be, another group of respondents were approached either from the selected house or from other houses located on the selected street for the purpose of credibility and accuracy of this study

Ikeja LGA according to the 2006 census has a population of 317,614; calculating the adjusted sample size for Ikeja LGA was as follows.

$$n = \frac{384}{1 + \left(\frac{384}{317,614}\right)}$$

Therefore the adjusted sample size is 383.5, approximately 384.

Finally, **calculating the sample size adjusted by response rate**

Substitute **384** for *n* and **95** for *re%* in the following formula

$$n^a = \frac{n \times 100}{re\%}$$

$$\text{Therefore, } n^a = \frac{384 \times 100}{95} = 404.21$$

The sample size for Ikeja LGA is 404 respondents.

Therefore the total sample size for the study was 808 respondents.

Table 3.4 List of Streets Systematically Selected in Ward B (Alade) at Ikeja LGA and Distribution of Sample Size

Akintoye Shogunle Street	First 29 houses X 2 respondents = 58 respondents
Balogun Street	First 29 houses X 2 respondents = 58 respondents
Dipeolu Street	First 29 houses X 2 respondents = 58 respondents
Johnson Street	First 29 houses X 2 respondents = 58 respondents
Obokun Street	First 29 houses X 2 respondents = 58 respondents
Orishe Street	First 29 houses X 2 respondents = 58 respondents
Tinuade Close	First 29 houses X 2 respondents = 58 respondents
Total	406 respondents

Table 3.4 indicates the distribution of the sample size across the systematically selected streets at Ward B (Alade), Ikeja LGA. In order to practically reach the respondents at Ward B (Alade), Ikeja LGA, the first twenty nine (29) houses on each of the selected street was systematically selected (with house numbers) in order to eliminate bias, from which 2 respondents were selected, totaling four hundred and six (406) respondents. Finally, the total respondents for this study from the combined distribution of sample size by streets in Agege LGA and Ikeja LGA was $408+408=$ **816 respondents**.

The multi-stage sampling technique was used because more than one sampling method was combined in order to arrive at a finite representative sample size for the study. The first stage (1st stage) involved the usage of purposive sampling technique which focused on Lagos state as the location used for this study. Particularly, the purposive sampling technique served as an important guide in the context of this study as ensured that only Smartphone users with a considerable access level to the internet were focused on for the credibility of result for this study. In the second stage (2nd stage), the simple random sampling technique was adopted in order to select two (2) Local Government Areas. Two local government areas were selected randomly through simple random sampling. Simple random sampling technique was necessary because it gave equal chance of selection to all the Local Government Areas in Lagos State. Agege and Ikeja Local Government Areas were selected locations for the study. The third stage (3rd stage) involved the random selection of one (1) ward from each Local Government Area, this was done so as to give all the wards equal chance of selection. Agege Local Government has eleven (11) wards, Wards B

(Dopemu) was randomly selected through simple random sampling (balloting) while at Ikeja Local Government Area, there are eight (8) wards, Ward B (Alade) was randomly selected through simple random sampling (balloting). The fourth stage (4th Stage) adopted the systematic sampling to select every fourth (4th) street from the wards selected; this was done because it gave equal chance of selection to every street in every selected ward. From Ward B (Dopemu) at Agege Local Government Area, there are 32 Streets (See Table 3.1); every 4th street was systematically selected leading to the selection of eight (8) streets, which were **Adegbola Street, Akinwunmi Street, Buluro Street, Ogunjobi Street, Olorunlogbon Street, Salako Street, Subuola Street and Union Road (New)**. From Ward B (Alade) at Ikeja Local Government there are 29 streets (See Table 3.2), every 4th street was systematically selected, seven (7) streets were selected, and they were: **Akintoye Shogunle Street, Balogun Street, Dipeolu Street, Johnson Street, Obokun Street, Orishe Street and Tinuade Close**.

It is very important to note that the purposive sampling technique was a major guide for this study as its strength was not just centered on making use of Lagos state as the most convenient location for this study because of its high economic related activities with respondents from various social classes but particularly ensured that internet users amongst the category of all the respondents in Lagos State were being studied to positively enhance the purpose of this research exercise.

List of Wards at Agege Local Government

1. Ward A (Isale Oja)
2. **Ward B (Dopemu)**
3. Ward C (Papa-Uku)
4. Ward D (Papa-Asafa)
5. Ward E (Alagba/Oyewole)
6. Ward F (Okekoto/Atobaje)
7. Ward G (Keke)
8. Ward H (Darocha)
9. Ward I (Oke-Oba)
10. Ward J (Orile Aege)
11. Ward K (Isale Odo/Abekoko)

Source: Agege Local Government

List of Wards at Ikeja Local Government

1. Ward A (Orile Ikeja)
2. **Ward B (Alade)**
3. Ward C (Onilekere)
4. Ward C (Onipetesi)
5. Ward D (Anifowoshe)
6. Ward E (Seriki Aro)
7. Alausa Ward F
8. Ward G (Coker/M.K.O Gardens)

Source: Ikeja Local Government

Table 3.1 List of Streets in Ward B (Dopemu) at Agege LGA

Ward B (Dopemu)
1. Abeokuta Street
2. Adebisi Ayopo Street
3. Adegbite Street
4. Adegbola Street
5. Adeyoola Street
6. Ajakaiye Street
7. Akinsola Street
8. Akinwunmi Street
9. Alfa Yusuf Street
10. Arigidi Street
11. Bello Ajare Street
12. Buluro Street
13. Ifelodun Street
14. Ogeretedo Street
15. Ogunbambi Street
16. Ogunjobi Street
17. Ojualale Street
18. Olasola Street
19. Old Union Rd
20. Olorunlogbon Street
21. Olusesi Street
22. Onipetesi Street
23. Oniwaya Street
24. Salako Street
25. Shitta Street
26. Somoorin Street
27. Sonaya Street
28. Subuola Street
29. Sunday Street
30. Surulere Street
31. Temidire Street
32. Union Road (New)

Source: Agege Local Government

Table 3.2 List of Streets in Ward B (Alade) at Ikeja LGA

Ward B (Alade)
1. Adekunbi Street
2. Adeleke Street
3. Adesine by Left Joh Olugha Street, by Left
4. Akintoye Shogunle Street
5. Alade Avenue
6. Alade Close
7. Arapasanwo Street
8. Balogun Street
9. Bayode Oluwole Street
10. Bisi Ogabi Street
11. Dele Dosunmi
12. Dipeolu Street
13. Fadeyi Aladura Street
14. Gbajobi Street
15. Gbamisola Street
16. Johnson Street
17. Ladipo Kasumu Street
18. Ladipo Street
19. Morenike Street
20. Obokun Street
21. Ogun Street
22. Oluwaleyinmu Street
23. Orija Lane
24. Orishe Street
25. Philip Oluwole Lane
26. Sanyaolu Street
27. Soji Adepegba Street
28. Tinuade Close
29. Wemu Akinsola Close

Source: Ikeja Local Government

3.4 Research Instrument

The research instrument that was used for this study was the structured questionnaire, it is a cost effective way to gather primary data from a cross section of a population. The questionnaire had five sections, section A measured the demographic details of the respondents while section B, C and D used a 5-point Likert Scale to (Strong Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), Strongly Disagree (SD), Undecided (U)) indicate the level to which respondents agreed with the statements in the questionnaire. Section B measured respondents' awareness of Smartphone brands advertised online, Section C measured respondents' awareness of Smartphone brands advertised online. Section D will measured respondents' perception of quality, durability and class in Smartphones advertised online. Section E elicited the influence factors such as price, features and social influence have on Smartphones advertised online. The structured questionnaire for the purpose of this research work was developed by the researcher for accurate measurements of the research variables in this study by examining the research questions, objectives and the hypothesis and structuring the questionnaire to match up with them.

3.5 Validity of Research Instrument

Face validity was carried out by three experts in the field of research in mass communication, two advertising practitioners including the study supervisor. This was done in order to ensure the instrument measured what it was designed to measure. Content validity by the researcher and colleagues through comparison with similar studies and other literature was also used to realign the variables in the study. Also, the suggestion of a research methodologist alongside the adoption of previously used questionnaires served as a guide in the development of the questionnaire which was used for this study. Moreover, suggestions and ideas from relevant literature related to this study was incorporated in the final draft of the instrument to ensure content validity before administering the research instruments to the respondents.

3.7 Reliability of Research Instrument

Testing the reliability of a research instrument is important because it helps to ascertain the strength and usability of a data collection instrument. A pilot study was conducted at Sagamu and the feedback from respondents was used to perfect the research instrument. Furthermore, the Cronbach's Alpha value was generated for the questionnaire in order to indicate the degree of internal consistency that the structured questionnaire has. The composite Cronbach's Alpha was 0.945 which indicated that the instrument was highly reliable.

3.8 Administration of Research Instrument

The structured questionnaire was administered by the researcher and four research assistants. These research assistants were trained to ensure they administered the copies of the questionnaire appropriately. The structured copies of the questionnaire administered for the purpose of this study were administered to respondents by approaching them in their various selected houses within the context of this study and collected by hand.

3.9 Method of Data Analysis

Data generated from the study was presented using frequency counts, mean, standard deviation, tables and charts. Linear regression analysis and multiple linear regression were used to test the hypotheses of the study. Regression showed the level of influence that the independent variable has on the dependent as it is indicated in the research hypotheses of this study.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA ANALYSIS, RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.0. Introduction

This chapter presents the analysis, interpretation and discussion of findings. This study examined the role of online advertising in consumers' perception and purchase decision of Smartphones. 816 copies of the questionnaire were distributed, 650 were retrieved and validated, making up 79.7 percent of response rate. Descriptive analysis was carried out with the aid of mean, standard deviation, frequency counts, percentages, tables and charts, while the inferential statistical analysis was carried out by adopting simple linear and multiple linear regression. Here, the demographic details of the respondents, thereafter detailed questionnaire items that answered the research questions which guided the study and finally, testing the hypotheses postulated for the study.

4.1 Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Table 4.1: Demographic Features of Respondents

Demographic Features	Frequency	Percentage (%)	
Age	15-24	427	65.7
	25-30	96	14.8
	31-40	40	6.2
	41-50	37	5.7
	51 and above	50	7.7
	Total	650	100.0
Gender	Male	304	46.8
	Female	346	53.2
	Total	650	100.0

Table 4.1 indicates that the predominant age category among the study participants was 15-24 (n=427, 65.7%). This suggests that majority of the study participants were young while few older participants were in the age categories of 41-50 (n=37, 5.7%) and 51 and above (n=50, 7.7%). The respondents were not equally represented by gender; female respondents (n=346, 53.2%) had more representation than their males counterparts (n=304, 46.8%).

Figure 4.1 Respondents who Own Smartphones and the Duration of Ownership

Figure 4.1 depicts that 91.7% of the respondents indicated that they had Smartphones. This implies that majority of the study participants use Smartphone devices. In addition, Figure 4.1 shows that almost half (45.1%) of the respondents had owned Smartphones for 1 to 5 years. This depicts that many study participants who owned Smartphones had not owned it for up to a decade.

Figure 4.2 Smartphone Brands presently being used

From Figure 4.2, the common Smartphone brands presently being used by the respondents were *Samsung* (23.4%), *Blackberry* (21.1%) and *Techno* (13.4%). However, the least common Smartphone brands among respondents were *Nokia* and *Philips*.

Table 4.2: Awareness of Online Advertisements

Items	TVGEX	GEX	LEX	VLEX	NT	Mean	SD
I am aware of online advertisements	411 (63.2)	87 (13.4)	132 (20.3)		20 (3.1)	4.34	1.00
I spend less time concentrating on online advertisements	312 (48.0)	192 (29.5)	130 (20.0)		16 (2.5)	4.21	0.93
I see online advertisements regularly	279 (42.9)	132 (20.3)	117 (18.0)	16 (2.5)	106 (16.3)	3.71	1.45
Online advertisements are attractive	90 (29.2)	152 (23.4)	159 (24.5)	125 (19.2)	24 (3.7)	3.55	1.20
I spend much time concentrating on online advertisements	63 (9.7)	23 (3.5)	209 (32.2)	155 (23.8)	200 (30.8)	2.38	1.23
Total Average Weighted Mean						3.64	1.16

KEY: TVGEX=To a very great extent, GEX=Great extent, LEX=Low extent, VLEX=Very Low extent, NA=Not at all. Decision Rule if mean is ≤ 1.49 =Not at all; 1.5 to 2.49 = VLEX; 2.5 to 3.49 =LEX; 3.5 to 4.49 = GEX; 4.5 to 5 = TVGEX

Table 4.2 shows that over half of the respondents were aware of online advertisements (Total Average Weighted Mean= 3.64, SD=1.16). This implies that generally, residents of Agege and Ikeja local government area of Lagos state were exposed to online advertising. Specifically, respondents usually spent less time concentrating on online advertisements to a great extent (Mean= 4.21, SD=0.93), however saw online advertisements regularly at a maximum level (Mean=3.71, SD=1.45) and averagely perceived online advertisements as being very much attractive (Mean=3.55, SD= 1.20). However, over half of the respondents spent much time concentrating on online advertisements at a minimal level (Mean= 2.38, SD=1.23). This suggests that Lagos State residents despite being aware attracted and exposed to online advertisements regularly, spend less time concentrating on online advertisements.

4.2 Research Question One: What is the level of consumers' exposure to online advertising?

Table 4.3 Exposure to Smartphone Online Advertising

Items	TVGE X	GEX	LEX	VLEX	NT	Mean	SD	Average Mean
Social Media Advertising								
Smartphone advertisements are received on the social media	311 (47.8)	153 (23.5)	50 (7.7)	44 (6.8)	92 (14.2)	3.84	1.44	Mean=3.77 (SD=1.41)
Competing brands of Smartphone advertisements are seen on the social media	231 (35.5)	218 (33.5)	65 (10.0)	44 (6.8)	92 (14.2)	3.70	1.38	
Search Engine Advertising								
I use search engines (e.g. Google, Bing, Yahoo, Ask.com)	352 (54.2)	238 (36.6)	17 (2.6)	20 (3.1)	23 (3.5)	4.35	0.94	Mean=3.67 (SD=1.25)
Competing brands of Smartphone advertisements are seen on search engine results	292 (44.9)	202 (31.1)	25 (3.8)	81 (12.5)	50 (7.7)	3.93	1.29	
Smartphone results on search engines appear from advertisers and marketers	125 (19.2)	177 (27.2)	149 (22.9)	126 (19.4)	73 (11.2)	3.24	1.28	
I search for Smartphones on search engines	152 (23.4)	177 (27.2)	91 (14.0)	92 (14.2)	138 (21.2)	3.17	1.47	
Mobile Advertising								
Smartphone advertisements are received on phone applications (Apps)	196 (30.2)	203 (31.2)	137 (21.1)	19 (2.9)	95 (14.6)	3.59	1.34	
Smartphone advertisements are sent through mobile devices	213 (32.8)	53 (8.2)	269 (41.4)	65 (10.0)	50 (7.7)	3.48	1.25	Mean=3.21

Competing brands of 177	148	193	20	112	3.40	1.37	(SD=1.42)	
Smartphone advertisements are seen on phone applications (Apps)	(27.2)	(22.8)	(29.7)	(3.1)	(17.2)			
Competing brands of 119	127	170	-	234	2.84	1.53		
Smartphone advertisements are sent through SMS	(18.3)	(19.5)	(26.2)	(36.0)				
Smartphone advertisements are received on SMS	123	139	89	48	251	2.75	1.59	
	(18.9)	(21.4)	(13.7)	(7.4)	(38.6)			
E-mail Advertising								
I receive e-mails	154	136	157	17	186	3.08	1.52	
	(23.7)	(20.9)	(24.2)	(2.6)	(28.6)			
Unsolicited or unwanted e-mail	128	88	206	40	188	2.89	1.46	
Smartphone advertisements are received	(19.7)	(13.5)	(31.7)	(6.2)	(28.9)			
Smartphone advertisements are displayed in the e-mail window	88	117	164	68	213	2.69	1.43	
	(13.5)	(18.0)	(25.2)	(10.5)	(32.8)		Mean=2.77 (SD=1.49)	
Competing brands of 101	148	95	34	272	2.65	1.57		
Smartphone advertisements are presented in e-mail windows	(15.5)	(22.8)	(14.6)	(5.2)	(41.8)			
Pop-up Smartphone advertisements are sent to e-mail windows	115	23	212	38	262	2.52	1.48	
	(17.7)	(3.5)	(32.6)	(5.8)	(40.3)			
Total Average Weighted Mean							Mean=3.26	
							(SD=1.40)	

KEY: TVGEX=To a very great extent, GEX=Great extent, LEX=Low extent, VLEX=Very Low extent, NA=Not at all. Decision Rule if mean is ≤ 1.49 =Not at all; 1.5 to 2.49 = VLEX; 2.5 to 3.49 =LEX; 3.5 to 4.49 = GEX; 4.5 to 5 = TVGEX

Table 4.3 shows that over half of the respondents exposed to online Smartphone advertising to a low extent (Total Average Weighted Mean= 3.26, SD=1.40). This suggests that Lagos State residents in Agege and Ikeja local government areas are not fully exposed to online advertisements. The study participants had however been averagely exposed to social media

advertising of Smartphones to a great extent (Mean= 3.77, SD= 1.41) and Search engine advertising to a great extent (Mean=3.67, SD=1.25), while the study participants had been averagely exposed to mobile advertising of Smartphones (Mean= 3.21, SD=1.42) and e-mail advertising of Smartphones to a low extent (Mean=2.77, SD=1.49). This suggests that Lagos residents were exposed more to online advertising through social media and search engines while mobile and email means of advertisements among Lagos State residents were not adopted to a high extent.

4.3 Research Question Two: To what extent are consumers aware of Smartphone brands advertised online?

Figure 4.3 Awareness of Smartphone Brands Advertised Online

From Figure 4.3, majority of the respondents were aware of *iPhone* Smartphone brand (59.1%) through online advertising, while many were aware of *Samsung* (48.6%), *HTC* (46.8%), *Infinix* (46.5%) and *Techno* (46.3%) through online advertising. However, few study participants were aware of *Sony* (27.7%), *Philips* (15.8%) and *Alcatel* (9.7%) through online advertising. This suggests that *Sony*, *Philips* and *Alcatel* Smartphone brands did not have a dominant online advertising presence among the respondents, while *iPhone*, *Samsung*, *Infinix* and *Techno* had an almost averagely dominant online advertising presence among Lagos State residents.

4.4 Research Question Three: To what extent do consumers pay attention to online advertisements?

Table 4.4: Attention to Online Advertisements

Items	TVGE X	GEX	LEX	VLEX	NT	Mea n	SD
Graphics quality of online advertisements attract me	318 (48.9)	162 (24.9)	76 (11.7)	20 (3.1)	74 (11.4)	3.97	1.32
Pictures displayed via online advertisements attract me	169 (26.0)	250 (38.5)	102 (15.7)	-	129 (19.8)	3.51	1.40
Wordings and lettering style of online advertisements attract me	155 (23.8)	150 (23.1)	144 (22.2)	138 (21.2)	63 (9.7)	3.30	1.30
Pop up messages of online advertisements attract me	134 (20.6)	151 (23.2)	102 (15.7)	91 (14.0)	172 (26.5)	2.98	1.50
Advertisements sent to my mail attracts me	40 (6.2)	105 (16.2)	188 (28.9)	73 (11.2)	244 (37.5)	2.42	1.30
Total Average Weighted Mean						3.24	1.37

KEY: TVGEX= To a very great extent, GEX=Great extent, LEX=Low extent, VLEX=Very Low extent, NA=Not at all. Decision Rule if mean is ≤ 1.49 =Not at all; 1.5 to 2.49 = VLEX; 2.5 to 3.49 =LEX; 3.5 to 4.49 = GEX; 4.5 to 5 = TVGEX

Table 4.4 shows that the study participants did not pay so much attention to online advertisements to a low extent (Total Average Weighted Mean= 3.24, SD=1.37). This implies that Lagos State residents on average paid attention to online advertisements to a low extent. However, the study over half of the study participants paid attention to graphic quality (Mean=3.97, SD=1.32) and pictures displayed (Mean=3.51, SD=1.40) to a great extent, while wordings and lettering style (Mean=3.30, SD=1.30) and pop up messages of online advertisements (Mean=2.98, SD=1.50) were paid attention to, to a low extent. Finally, advertisements sent to respondents' emails affects them in a minimum manner (Mean=2.42, SD=1.30). These suggest that Lagos State residents pay attention to graphic

quality and pictures in online advertisements more than wordings and lettering, pop up messages and advertisements sent to their email addresses.

4.5 Research Question Four: What is consumers' perception (Price, features, quality, durability, class) of Smartphones?

Table 4.5: Consumer Perception of Smartphone

Items	SA	A	D	SD	U	Mean	SD	Average Mean
Feature								
E-mail management are better with Smartphones	489 (75.2)	161 (24.8)	-	-	-	4.75	0.43	
Smartphones make sharing of information and resources easier	530 (81.5)	99 (15.2)	-	-	21 (3.2)	4.72	0.77	
Smartphone applications are useful	452 (69.5)	198 (30.5)	-	-	-	4.70	0.46	
Downloading and uploading of files are efficient on Smartphones	470 (72.3)	159 (24.5)	-	21 (3.2)	-	4.66	0.65	
Smartphones are used for management of personal activities	411 (63.2)	239 (36.8)	-	-	-	4.63	0.48	Mean=4.29
Smartphones features enhance inter and intra personal communication	455 (70.0)	134 (20.6)	20 (3.1)	-	41 (6.3)	4.48	1.03	(SD=0.91)
Features for playing games on Smartphones is needed	317 (48.8)	199 (30.6)	49 (7.5)	68 (10.5)	17 (2.6)	4.12	1.10	
Feature for playing music on Smartphones is needed	329 (50.6)	167 (25.7)	68 (10.5)	69 (10.6)	17 (2.6)	4.11	1.12	
I like Smartphones with big screens	342 (52.6)	166 (25.5)	37 (5.7)	34 (5.2)	71 (10.9)	4.04	1.33	
I like Smartphones that are colourful	285 (43.8)	147 (22.6)	110 (16.9)	58 (8.9)	50 (7.7)	3.86	1.28	
I like Smartphones with buttons	131 (20.2)	125 (19.2)	156 (24.0)	154 (23.7)	84 (12.9)	3.10	1.32	
Durability								
Smartphone screens are strong	407 (62.6)	243 (37.4)	-	-	-	4.63	0.48	
Smartphones that last 2 years are durable	254 (39.1)	361 (55.5)	-	-	35 (5.4)	4.23	0.91	
Smartphones are durable	182 (28.0)	431 (66.3)	-	-	37 (5.7)	4.11	0.88	Mean=4.15 (SD=0.99)

Smartphones that last 1 year are durable	268 (41.2)	310 (47.7)	-	-	72 (11.1)	4.08	1.19	
Smartphones that last longer than 3 years are durable	223 (34.3)	355 (54.6)	-	-	72 (11.1)	4.01	1.16	
Manufacturers make durable Smartphones	212 (32.6)	332 (51.1)	-	-	106 (16.3)	3.84	1.33	
Class								
The type of Smartphone someone uses can give someone respect	399 (61.4)	168 (25.8)	25 (3.8)	37 (5.7)	21 (3.2)	4.36	1.02	
A rare luxurious Smartphone can make someone unique	338 (52.0)	238 (36.6)	-	74 (11.4)	-	4.29	0.94	Mean=4.01 (SD=1.10)
Smartphones can make you important among your peers	254 (39.1)	239 (36.8)	50 (7.7)	107 (16.5)	-	3.98	1.06	
Luxury fashion Smartphones are the true definition of Smartphones	234 (36.0)	76 (11.7)	87 (13.4)	220 (33.8)	33 (5.1)	3.40	1.39	
Quality								
Smartphone quality is reliable	311 (47.8)	224 (34.5)	70 (10.8)	24 (3.7)	21 (3.2)	4.20	0.99	
Smartphone quality can be determined by the performance of manufacturers' past products	322 (49.5)	159 (24.5)	81 (12.5)	88 (13.5)	-	4.10	1.07	Mean=3.75 (SD=1.07)
Smartphone quality is determined by manufacturers' warranty	296 (45.5)	147 (22.6)	155 (23.8)	52 (8.0)	-	4.06	1.01	
Smartphone quality is determined by details presented in advertisements	185 (28.5)	199 (30.6)	166 (25.5)	84 (12.9)	16 (2.5)	3.70	1.09	
Quality is reflected in the beauty of the Smartphone	157 (24.2)	139 (21.4)	183 (28.2)	152 (23.4)	19 (2.9)	3.40	1.17	
Quality is reflected in the weight of the Smartphone	109 (16.8)	38 (5.8)	286 (44.0)	196 (30.2)	21 (3.2)	3.03	1.08	
Price								
Expensive Smartphone offer more features than non-expensive ones	331 (50.9)	251 (38.6)	25 (3.8)	43 (6.6)	-	4.34	0.84	
Expensive Smartphones are symbol of class in the society	368 (56.6)	56 (8.6)	184 (28.3)	23 (3.5)	19 (2.9)	4.12	1.11	
Smartphone price means quality	273 (42.0)	121 (18.6)	89 (13.7)	167 (25.7)	-	3.77	1.24	Mean=3.69 (SD=1.15)
Expensive Smartphones are original products	237 (36.5)	180 (27.7)	91 (14.0)	125 (19.2)	17 (2.6)	3.76	1.21	
Smartphone price matters	183 (28.2)	87 (13.4)	182 (28.0)	165 (25.4)	33 (5.1)	3.34	1.27	

Non-expensive Smartphones are durable	161	167	134	106	82	3.34	1.34	
	(24.8)	(25.7)	(20.6)	(16.3)	(12.6)			
Non-expensive Smartphones benefit high class gatherings	62	193	223	134	38	3.16	1.05	
	(9.5)	(29.7)	(34.3)	(20.6)	(5.8)			
Total Average Weighted Mean							Mean=4.01	(SD=1.02)

KEY: SA=Strongly Agree, A=Agree, D=Disagree, SD=Strongly Disagree, U=Undecided. Decision Rule if mean is ≤ 1.49 =Undecided; 1.5 to 2.49 =Strongly Disagree; 2.5 to 3.49 =Disagree; 3.5 to 4.49 = Agree; 4.5 to 5 = Strongly Agree

Table 4.5 shows that generally, respondents averagely agreed they had a positive perception of Smartphone (Total Average Weighted Mean= 4.01, SD=1.02). Individually, the study participants averagely agreed with the items on the *Feature* scale (Mean= 4.29, SD=0.91), *Durability* scale (Mean= 4.15, SD=0.99), *Class* scale (Mean= 4.01, SD=1.10), *Quality* scale (Mean= 3.75, SD=1.07) and *Price* scale (Mean= 3.69, SD=1.15). This suggests that respondents had a better perception of Smartphone features than durability, class, quality and price. This further indicates that Lagos State residents perceive Smartphones more with their functionality, durability and class endowing capabilities.

4.6 Research Question Five: What relationship exists between perception (price, features, quality, durability, class) and purchase decision of Smartphones?

Table 4.6: Relationship between Purchase Decision and Perception of Smartphones Advertised Online

Statements	SA	A	D	SD	U	Mean	SD
Quality of advertised Smartphones Online determines my purchase decision	322	52	50	80	46	3.96	1.30
	(49.5)	23.4)	(7.7)	(12.3)	(7.1)		
Durability of advertised Smartphones Online determines my purchase decision	256	218	70	60	46	3.89	1.22
	(39.4)	(33.5)	(10.8)	(9.2)	(7.1)		
Features of advertised Smartphones determines my purchase decision	258	193	114	20	65	3.86	1.26
	(39.7)	(29.7)	17.5)	(3.1)	(10.0)		
Class of advertised Smartphones Online determines my purchase decision	191	192	111	91	65	3.54	1.31
	(29.4)	(29.5)	(17.1)	(14.0)	(10.0)		

Price of advertised Smartphones Online determines my purchase decision	198	229	39	75	109	3.51	1.45
	30.5)	(35.2)	(6.0)	(11.5)	(16.8)		
Smartphone(s) purchased by me is as a result of its seen advertisements online	194	78	209	73	96	3.31	1.39
	(29.8)	(12.0)	(32.2)	(11.2)	(14.8)		
Total Average Weighted Mean						3.68	1.32

KEY: SA=Strongly Agree, A=Agree, D=Disagree, SD=Strongly Disagree, U=Undecided. Decision Rule if mean is ≤ 1.49 =Undecided; 1.5 to 2.49 =Strongly Disagree; 2.5 to 3.49 =Disagree; 3.5 to 4.49 = Agree; 4.5 to 5 = Strongly Agree

From Table 4.6, the study participants averagely agreed that there is a relationship between purchase decision and perception of Smartphone advertised online (Total Average Weighted Mean= 3.68, SD=1.32). This indicates that Lagos State residents perceive that there is a relationship between purchase decision and perception of Smartphones by quality, durability, features, class and price.

Table 4.7: Consumer Purchase Decision of Smartphones Advertised Online

Items	SA	A	D	SD	U	Mean	SD
More information is sought on Smartphones advertised online	361	195		20	74	4.15	1.30
	(55.5)	(30.0)		(3.1)	(11.4)		
Smartphones advertised online increases awareness of Smartphone brands	337	224			89	4.11	1.32
	(51.8)	(34.5)			(13.7)		
Smartphones advertised online are considered by consumers	324	214		41	71	4.04	1.32
	(49.8)	(32.9)		(6.3)	(10.9)		
Advertising Smartphones online helps consumer evaluation	321	148	40	16	125	3.81	1.53
	(49.4)	(22.8)	(6.2)	(2.5)	19.2)		
Consumers purchase Smartphones advertised online	180	225	85	37	123	3.46	1.43
	(27.7)	(34.6)	(13.1)	(5.7)	(18.9)		
Total Average Weighted Mean						3.92	1.38

KEY: SA=Strongly Agree, A=Agree, D=Disagree, SD=Strongly Disagree, U=Undecided. Decision Rule if mean is ≤ 1.49 =Undecided; 1.5 to 2.49 =Strongly Disagree; 2.5 to 3.49 =Disagree; 3.5 to 4.49 = Agree; 4.5 to 5 = Strongly Agree

Table 4.7 shows that respondents averagely agreed from a general standpoint that consumers have a positive perception towards consumer purchase decision of Smartphones advertised online (Total Average Weighted Mean= 3.92, SD=1.38). Specifically, in the consumer purchase decision process, online search of information on Smartphones was perceived to be most important, followed by increased awareness of Smartphones brands, consideration of Smartphones advertised online, evaluation of Smartphones advertised online and finally purchase of Smartphones advertised online. This reflects the stages of purchase decision that Lagos State residents may go through, it indicates that purchase of Smartphones advertised online occurs last after information have been gathered on the advertised Smartphone thereby, enhancing Lagos residents' awareness, consideration and evaluation of Smartphones advertised online.

4.7 Test of Hypotheses

Decision Rule

The level of significance set for this study is 0.05. The hypotheses for this study assume that there is a relationship between the variables being considered. If the p-value or the probability value is higher than pre-set level, the hypothesis stated in alternative form will be rejected. On the other hand, if the p-value is less than or equal to 0.05, the hypothesis will be accepted.

Hypothesis One: Consumers' exposure to online advertising significantly influences awareness of Smartphone brands advertised online.

Table 4.8a Model Summary for the Influence of Email Advertising, Search Engine Advertising, Mobile Advertising and Social Media Advertising on Awareness of Smartphone Brands Advertised Online

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.603 ^a	0.363	0.359	3.97054

a. Predictors: (Constant), Social Media Advertising, Email Advertising, Search Engine Advertising, Mobile Advertising

Table 4.8b Multiple Linear Regression showing the Influence of Email Advertising, Search Engine Advertising, Mobile Advertising and Social Media Advertising on Awareness of Smartphone Brands Advertised Online

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	32.527	.661		49.216	0.000
	Email Advertising	-.181	.034	-.184	-5.273	0.000
	Search Engine Advertising	-.068	.055	-.046	-1.226	0.221
	Mobile Advertising	-.286	.039	-.276	-7.306	0.000
	Social Media Advertising	-.815	.091	-.331	-8.940	0.000

a. Dependent Variable: Awareness of Smartphone Brands Advertised Online
ANOVA= 0.000

Table 4.8b indicates that the representation of consumers' exposure to online advertising jointly influences awareness of Smartphone brands advertised online (ANOVA, $p < 0.05$). This suggests that when email advertising, search engine advertising, mobile advertising and social media advertising are adopted to expose consumers to online advertising, it leads to awareness of Smartphones advertised online. From the individual perspective, it is only search engine advertising that does not have an individual significant influence on awareness of Smartphone brands advertised online ($p = 0.221$). This suggests that email advertising, mobile advertising and social media advertising have individual significant influence on awareness of Smartphone brands advertised online ($p < 0.05$). This points out that among the respondents; it is email advertising, mobile advertising and social media advertising that increases awareness of Smartphone brands advertised online.

However, the negative correlation coefficient and slope shows that an increase in email advertising, mobile advertising and social media advertising lead to a reduction in awareness of Smartphone brands advertised online vice versa. This might imply that as Lagos residents are exposed to online advertising adopting email advertising, mobile advertising and social media advertising, their awareness of Smartphone brands advertised online reduces probably because of saturation effect that might have been caused by over-exposure to online advertising. The model in Table 4.8a could predict 36.3 percent ($R^2 = 0.363$) of variation of influence of awareness of Smartphone brands advertised online. The model accounts for a significant proportion of awareness of Smartphone brands advertised online variance ($F(4,645) = 91.934, p < 0.05$). Hence, the hypothesis is accepted.

Hypothesis Two: Attention to online advertisements significantly influences perception (price, features, quality, durability and class) of Smartphone brands.

Table 4.9a Model Summary for the Influence of Attention to Online Advertisements on Perception of Price of Smartphone brands

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.009 ^a	0.000	-0.001	4.87215

a. Predictors: (Constant), Attention to Online Advertisements

Table 4.9b Simple Linear Regression showing the Influence of Attention to Online Advertisements on Perception of Price of Smartphones

Model	Unstandardized		Standardize d	t	Sig.	
	Coefficients					
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
	(Constant)	22.994	.588		39.095	0.000
1	Attention to Online Advertisements	0.009	0.039	0.009	0.234	0.815

a. Dependent Variable: Price of Smartphones

Table 4.9b indicates that attention to online advertisements does not significantly influence perception of price of Smartphones ($p=0.815$). This indicates that Lagos State residents' perception of price of Smartphones is not influenced by paying attention to online advertisements. Therefore, the hypothesis that attention to online advertisements significantly influences perception of price of Smartphone brands is rejected.

Table 4.10a Model Summary for the Influence of Attention to Online Advertisements on Perception of Features of Smartphones

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.456 ^a	0.208	0.207	4.01009

a. Predictors: (Constant), Attention to Online Advertisements

Table 4.10b Simple Linear Regression showing the Influence of Attention to Online Advertisements on Perception of Features of Smartphones

Model	Unstandardized		Standardize d	t	Sig.
	Coefficients				
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	37.681	.484		77.837	0.000
1 Attention to Online Advertisements	0.420	0.032	0.456	13.059	0.000

a. Dependent Variable: Features of Smartphones

Table 4.10b shows that attention to online advertisements significantly influences perception of features of Smartphones ($p < 0.05$). This implies that Lagos State residents' perception of features of Smartphones is influenced by paying attention to online advertisements. This further suggests that when Lagos State residents pay attention to online advertisements, it has the potential to increase their perception of features of Smartphones. The positive correlation coefficient and slope ($\beta = 0.456$, $B = 0.420$) shows a positive moderate relationship between attention to online advertisements and perception of features of Smartphones, which suggests that an increase in attention to online advertisements leads to a proportional increase in the perception of features of Smartphones brands, vice versa. Table 4.10a shows that attention to online advertisements could explain 20.8 percent of variation of influence on perception of features of Smartphones ($R^2 = 0.208$) which is a significant amount of perception of features of Smartphone variance ($F(1, 648) = 170.550$, $T = 13.059$, $p < 0.05$). Therefore, the hypothesis that attention to online advertisements significantly influences perception of features of Smartphone brands is accepted.

Table 4.11a Model Summary for the Influence of Attention to Online Advertisements on Perception of Quality of Smartphones

Model Summary					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	
1	0.198 ^a	0.039	0.038	3.28477	

a. Predictors: (Constant), Attention to Online Advertisements

Table 4.11b Simple Linear Regression showing the Influence of Attention to Online Advertisements on Perception of Quality of Smartphones

Model		Unstandardized		Standardized t	Sig.
		Coefficients			
		B	Std. Error	Beta	
	(Constant)	17.480	.397	44.082	0.000
1	Attention to Online Advertisements	0.135	0.026	0.198	5.133

a. Dependent Variable: Quality of Smartphones

Table 4.11b depicts that attention to online advertisements significantly influences perception of Smartphone quality ($p < 0.05$). This implies that the perception of the respondents about the quality of Smartphones is influenced by paying attention to online advertisements. This further suggests that when Lagos residents pay attention to online advertisements, their perception of quality of Smartphones will likely increase. The positive correlation coefficient and slope ($\beta = 0.198$, $B = 0.135$) shows a low positive relationship between attention to online advertisements and perception of quality of Smartphones. Table 4.11a shows that attention to online advertisements could explain 3.9 percent of variation of influence on perception of quality of Smartphones ($R^2 = 0.039$) which is a significant amount of perception of quality of Smartphone variance ($F(1, 648) = 26.351$, $T = 5.133$, $p < 0.05$). Therefore, the hypothesis that attention to online advertisements significantly influences perception of quality of Smartphone brands is accepted.

Table 4.12a Model Summary for the Influence of Attention to Online Advertisements on Perception of Durability of Smartphones

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.287 ^a	0.082	0.081	3.30324

a. Predictors: (Constant), Attention to Online Advertisements

Table 4.12b Simple Linear Regression showing the Influence of Attention to Online Advertisements on Perception of Durability of Smartphones

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
	(Constant)	18.819	.399		47.194	.000
1	Attention to Online Advertisements	0.202	0.026	0.287	7.624	0.000

a. Dependent Variable: Durability of Smartphones

From Table 4.12b, attention to online advertisements significantly influences perception of durability of Smartphones ($p < 0.05$). This implies that Lagos State residents' perception of durability of Smartphones is influenced by paying attention to online advertisements. This further suggests that when Lagos residents pay attention to online advertisements, their perception of durability of Smartphones will likely increase. The positive correlation coefficient and slope ($\beta = 0.287$, $B = 0.202$) shows a low positive relationship between attention to online advertisements and perception of durability of Smartphones. Table 4.12a shows that attention to online advertisements could explain 8.2 percent of variation of influence on perception of durability of Smartphones ($R^2 = 0.082$) which is a significant amount of perception of durability of Smartphone variance ($F(1, 648) = 58.131$, $T = 7.624$, $p < 0.05$). Therefore, the hypothesis that attention to online advertisements significantly influences perception of durability of Smartphone brands is accepted.

Table 4.13a Model Summary for the Influence of Attention to Online Advertisements on Perception of Class of Smartphones

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.404 ^a	0.163	0.162	2.75270

a. Predictors: (Constant), Attention to Online Advertisements

Table 4.13b Simple Linear Regression showing the Influence of Attention to Online Advertisements on Perception of Class of Smartphones

Model		Unstandardized		Standardized	t	Sig.
		Coefficients				
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
	(Constant)	9.237	.332		27.795	0.000
1	Attention to Online Advertisements	0.248	0.022	0.404	11.227	0.000

a. Dependent Variable: Class of Smartphones

Table 4.13b shows that attention to online advertisements significantly influences perception of class of Smartphones ($p < 0.05$). This implies that Lagos State residents' perception of Smartphones as an object of class is influenced by paying attention to online advertisements. This further suggests that when Lagos State residents pay attention to online advertisements, their perception of Smartphones as an object of class will likely increase. The positive correlation coefficient and slope ($\beta = 0.404$, $B = 0.248$) shows a moderate positive relationship between attention to online advertisements and perception of class of Smartphones. Table 4.13a shows that attention to online advertisements could explain 16.3 percent of variation of influence on perception of class of Smartphones ($R^2 = 0.163$) which is a significant amount of perception of class of Smartphone variance ($F(1, 648) = 126.040$, $T = 11.227$, $p < 0.05$). Therefore, the hypothesis that attention to online advertisements significantly influences perception of class of Smartphones is accepted.

Hypothesis Three: Consumers' perception (price, features, quality, durability and class) of Smartphones significantly influences purchase decision of Smartphones.

Table 4.14a Model Summary for the Influence of Consumers' Perception of Price, Features, Quality, Durability and Class of Smartphones on Purchase Decision of Smartphones

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.850 ^a	0.722	0.720	2.58848

a. Predictors: (Constant), Class of Smartphones, Durability of Smartphones, Quality of Smartphones, Price of Smartphones, Features of Smartphones

Table 4.14b Multiple Linear Regression showing the Influence of Attention to Online Advertisements on Perception of Class of Smartphones

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
	(Constant)	-18.416	1.089	-16.903	0.000
	Price of Smartphones	0.072	0.023	0.071	3.111
	Features of Smartphones	0.433	0.035	0.399	12.451
1	Quality of Smartphones	0.081	0.037	0.055	2.202
	Durability of Smartphones	0.194	0.031	0.137	6.286
	Class of Smartphones	0.696	0.044	0.428	15.926

Dependent Variable: Purchase Decision of Smartphones

ANOVA=0.000

Table 4.14b indicates that consumers' perception of Smartphones jointly significantly influences (price, features, quality, durability and class) purchase decision of Smartphones (ANOVA, $p < 0.05$). This suggests that when perception of price, features, quality and durability of Smartphones are considered, purchase decision of Smartphones will likely occur among Lagos State residents. The correlation coefficient in Table 4.14a ($\beta = 0.850$) indicates a high relationship between consumers' perception of Smartphones and purchase decision of Smartphones. This implies that an increase in Lagos State residents' perception

of Smartphones will lead to a proportional increase in purchase decision of Smartphones. From the individual perspective, price ($\beta=0.071$, $p<0.05$), features ($\beta=0.399$, $p<0.05$), quality ($\beta=0.055$, $p<0.05$), durability ($\beta=0.137$, $p<0.05$) and class ($\beta=0.428$, $p<0.05$) of Smartphones had an individual positive significant influence on purchase decision of Smartphones ($p<0.05$). The model in Table 4.14a could predict 72.2 percent ($R^2=0.722$) of variation of influence of purchase decision of Smartphones. The model accounts for a significant proportion of purchase decision of Smartphones variance ($F(5,644) = 334.552$, $p<0.05$). Hence, the hypothesis is accepted.

4.2 Discussion of Findings

This study examined online advertising and consumers' perception on purchase decision of Smartphones, by adopting five objectives and three hypotheses. Eight hundred and sixteen (816) copies of the questionnaire were administered to residents in Lagos State; six hundred and fifty copies (650) were retrieved and used for analysis. The female ($n=346$, 53.2%) respondents were more represented than the male participants ($n=304$, 46.8%). In addition, majority of the study participants were young individuals (65.7%) while older participants were few. The study showed that majority (91.7%) of the study participants had been in possession of Smartphone devices, while almost half (45.1%) of the respondents had owned Smartphones for 1 to 5 years. The common Smartphone brands being used by the respondents were *Samsung* (23.4%), *Blackberry* (21.1%) and *Techno* (13.4%), while the least common Smartphone brands among respondents were *Nokia* and *Philips*. The discussion of findings will be carried out under the following paragraphs.

In accordance to the context of this research work, certain objectives were set to help guide the study. However, the first objective which was aimed at finding out about the level of consumers exposure to online advertisement revealed that Lagos State residents were aware of online advertisements to a great extent (Total Average Weighted Mean= 3.64, SD=1.16). While being aware, attracted and exposed to online advertisements regularly, Lagos State residents spent less time concentrating on online advertisements. These findings shows that online formats of advertisements catch the awareness of potential consumers, this is more important because online advertisements attract potential customers. These can be explained by the AIDA model which presupposes that for an advertisement to be successful, it has to catch customers' level of awareness. This is not surprising because Lagos residents might

have been exposed to online advertisements to a great extent. However, the level of Lagos State residents' awareness did not advance to the next level of interest as stipulated by the AIDA model; this might have been because Lagos residents spent less time concentrating on online advertisements. This condition might have occurred because of the amount of irrelevant advertisements that had been poorly targeted at uninterested Lagos State residents. Had it been that majority of online advertisements that Lagos State residents were exposed to was within their range of interests, the amount of time spent concentrating on online advertisements might have increased, hence stimulating their desire and action which could lead to purchase decision of products advertised online.

The second objective was set to test the exposure of consumers to smartphone online advertising as well as find out about the awareness of consumers towards smartphone brands advertised online

In this study, Lagos State residents were generally exposed to online Smartphone advertising to a low extent (Total Average Weighted Mean= 3.26, SD=1.40). Nevertheless, Lagos State residents had been exposed to social media advertising of Smartphones (Mean= 3.77, SD= 1.41) and Search engine advertising to a great extent (Mean=3.67, SD=1.25), while they had been exposed to mobile advertising of Smartphones (Mean= 3.21, SD=1.42) and e-mail advertising of Smartphones to a low extent (Mean=2.77, SD=1.49). The implication of this is that Lagos State residents were exposed to online advertising of Smartphones more through social media and search engines than mobile and email means of advertising Smartphones among Lagos State residents. Although, Lagos State residents were aware of online advertisements to a great extent, their exposure to online Smartphone advertising was to a low extent. This suggests that generally Smartphone advertisers and vendors have not adopted online platforms as major means of reaching their potential customers such as Lagos State residents. The least adopted online platforms for Smartphone online advertising which were mobile advertising and e-mail advertising may be because Smartphone manufacturers, advertisers and vendors may not have access to Lagos State residents' phone numbers and email addresses which may be used to accurately customize relevant Smartphone advertisements to Lagos State residents. In addition, Smartphone manufacturers can accurately target consumers by using application based advertisements which are delivered when Smartphone owners use such applications, this move could increase

exposure to online Smartphone advertisements and awareness of Smartphone brands advertised online.

Contrastingly, it appears that Smartphone manufacturers have chosen to use social media and search engine advertising to ensure exposure to their advertisements. This is logical because of the number of Lagos State residents that may be active social media users who may have customized their advertising experience on social media by indicating the categories of advertisements you would like to receive and unwanted likewise search engine such as Google, especially when signed in as a user monitors and exposes users to advertisements that are related to one's interests. These (social media and search engine) seem to be strategic as it affords Smartphone manufacturers the opportunity to reach large number of potential consumers especially Lagos State residents. This study is supported by Alves (2014) who pointed out that the most adopted formats of online advertising are social media and search engine. Lightcap and Peek (2012) assert that social media advertising is strategic because of action *spec* targeting, sponsored story advertising, and monetization of a growing mobile user base. Alves (2014) also asserts that paid searches displayed on search engines such as Google or Yahoo!, which are designed to display keyword search results to users for marketing communication purposes. This suggests that Smartphone advertisements appear first in search queries of Lagos residents in order to drive traffic to the websites of where details about the advertised Smartphones can be seen. Furthermore, the lack of exposure of Lagos State residents to Smartphone online advertisements through email may be because of its obtrusive characteristics, especially because they may be considered unsolicited as it is suggested by Todi (2008) that a successful online advertising should be unobtrusive. Todi (2008) indicates that for an online advertising to thrive it should afford people the ability to express their personalities; this supports the finding of this study because social media platforms are designed to help members express themselves interactively, hence exposure of unobtrusive advertisements to such may be positively received.

This study demonstrated that *Sony*, *Philips* and *Alcatel* Smartphone brands did not have a dominant online advertising presence, while 59.1 percent indicated were aware of *iPhone* online advertising, 48.6 percent for *Samsung*, 46.8 percent for *HTC*, and 46.5 percent for

Techno respectively. This shows that *iPhone*, *Samsung* and *HTC* have adopted online advertising strategy to increase awareness of their Smartphone brands. This is not surprising as *iPhone* and *Samsung* have the highest shipment till the last quarter of 2016 according to the International Data Corporation (2016). The AIDA model explains the extent of attention given to social media and search engine advertising of Smartphones. It highlights that Lagos State residents most probably were exposed to social media and search engine advertising based on the attention given to customizing their advertising experiences actively or passively based on their interest, desire which may ultimately lead to purchase of Smartphone devices.

The test of hypothesis one showed that consumers' exposure to online advertising jointly significantly influenced awareness of Smartphone brands advertised online ($R^2=0.363$, $\beta=0.603$, $p<0.05$). This suggests that a combined use of email, search engine, mobile and social media advertising significantly influenced awareness of Smartphone brands advertised online. A closer look at the individual proxies for online advertising indicated that search engine advertising does not significantly influence Lagos State residents' awareness of Smartphone brands advertised online ($p=0.221$). This indicates that Lagos State residents may not have customized their advertising preferences on search engines as this contradicts their earlier submission that they were exposed to Search engine advertising to a great extent (Mean=3.67, SD=1.25). However, email ($\beta= -0.184$, $p<0.05$), mobile ($\beta= -0.276$, $p<0.05$) and social media ($\beta= -0.331$, $p<0.05$) advertising had negative individual significant influence on awareness of Smartphone brands advertised online. This suggests that an increase in email, mobile and social media advertising led to a reduction in awareness of Smartphone brands advertised online vice versa. This might imply that as Lagos residents were exposed to online advertising through email, mobile and social media advertising, their awareness of Smartphone brands reduced probably because of saturation effect that might have been caused by over-exposure to online advertising and non-customization of advertising preferences and experiences.

Consumers' attention to online advertisements was to be realized in line with the third objective of this study. However, this study revealed that Lagos State residents generally paid attention to online advertising to a low extent (Total Average Weighted Mean= 3.24,

SD=1.37). Notably however, Lagos State residents paid attention to a great extent to graphic quality (Mean=3.97, SD=1.32) and pictures displayed (Mean=3.51, SD=1.40), while they paid low attention to wordings, lettering style and pop up messages on online advertisements. Lagos State residents also paid attention a very low extent to email advertisements (Mean=2.42, SD=1.30). This implies that Lagos State residents paid attention to graphic quality and pictures in online advertisements more than wordings and lettering, pop up messages and advertisements sent to their email addresses. It also means that Lagos State residents do not pay attention to the advertisement content in terms of wordings which is a dominant method of conveying advertisement messages on online platforms. From AIDA model's propositions, it can be suggested that since Lagos State residents generally paid little attention to online advertisements, such advertisements would not stimulate their interest, desire nor pro-active measures to acquiring such advertised products. It is noteworthy that Lagos State residents paid attention to a great extent to graphic quality and pictures without paying attention to the content in terms of letterings and wordings of the advertisement. This indicates that although it seemed that the online advertisements caught the attention of Lagos State residents but did not lead to interest, desire, nor action, therefore can be labeled ineffective.

The test of hypothesis two pointed out that attention to online advertisements by Lagos State residents does not significantly influence perception of price of Smartphones ($p=0.815$). However, attention to online advertisements significantly influenced perception of features of Smartphones ($R^2=0.208$, $\beta=0.456$, $p<0.05$), quality of Smartphones ($R^2=0.039$, $\beta=0.198$, $p<0.05$), durability of Smartphones ($R^2=0.082$, $\beta=0.287$, $p<0.05$) and class of Smartphones ($R^2=0.163$, $\beta=0.404$, $p<0.05$). These can be explained by the Gibson's theory of direct perception; this is because Lagos State residents' attention to online Smartphone advertisements gave them access to collect data about the Smartphones which is the phenomenon of interest to make detailed analysis. This also informed the perception of the Smartphone features, durability and Smartphone as object of class distinction. This suggests that Smartphone online advertisements that were perceived positively in terms of features, quality, durability and class have successfully loaded the sensory inputs of Lagos State residents with conditioning advertisements that led Lagos State residents to such a positive perception. Furthermore, the AIDA model suggests that having paid a significant attention

to online advertisements of Smartphones, Lagos State residents were interested in Smartphones' features, quality, durability and their class characteristics; these consequently according to the assumptions of AIDA model could progress into desire and action which is eventual purchase of such Smartphones.

Consumers' Perception of Smartphones (Price, Feature, Quality, Durability, and Class) and Consumer Purchase Decision was explored as part of the objectives of this study. It was however figured out that Lagos State residents generally agreed they had a positive perception of Smartphone (Total Average Weighted Mean= 4.01, SD=1.02). The study showed that Lagos State residents had the highest positive perception towards Smartphone features (Mean= 4.29, SD=0.91), followed by durability (Mean= 4.15, SD=0.99), class (Mean= 4.01, SD=1.10), and Quality (Mean= 3.75, SD=1.07), while they had the lowest positive perception of Smartphone price (Mean= 3.69, SD=1.15). This means that Lagos State residents perceive Smartphones more with their functionality, durability and class endowing capabilities.

Malviya, Saluja and Thakur (2013) were in agreement with this study because they found that pricing, features, brand preferences, social Influence as important factors which contribute to the purchase decision of Smartphones being advertised online. According to Malviya, Saluja and Thakur (2013) class acts as a status symbol and that features are considered by consumers; features form product specifications and are needed to conduct several tasks. In addition, Malviya et al (2013) noted that Smartphone manufacturers should focus on durability, because they are usually positively perceived in high end Smartphones. Nagarkoti also found that consumers would most likely consider Smartphones that enable them carry out tasks such as calling texting, listening to music and so on (features) and would also consider their economic capability (price). The Gibson's theory of direct perception helps to understand the direction of this finding because Smartphone online advertising had made Lagos State residents to have a high perception of their features because the Smartphone advertisements they had been exposed to had most likely concentrated on the features that makes each Smartphone unique, therefore engaging the mind of the consumers in such a way that they would consciously and unconsciously analyse Smartphone features in detail. This is also the case with durability and class. Smartphones that project large battery sizes in its advertisements are trying to communicate

durability and to have a positive perception that their Smartphones lasts long. With the Gibson's theory of direct perception, it makes us to understand consumers acquire information from their environment most especially from Smartphone advertisements, the projections of the Smartphones in terms of features, quality, durability and class go a long way to create some form of impression in the mind of consumers which may positively or negatively impact the success of a Smartphone brand.

The test of hypothesis three showed that consumers' perception (price, features, quality, durability and class) of Smartphones jointly significantly influenced purchase decision of Smartphones ($R^2=0.722$, $\beta=0.850$, $p<0.05$). This implies that when consumers' perception of price, features, quality durability an class of Smartphones are considered at the same time especially by Lagos State residents, purchase decision of Smartphones will be influenced. The test of hypothesis also indicated that that Lagos State residents' perception of price ($\beta=0.071$, $p<0.05$), features ($\beta=0.399$, $p<0.05$), quality ($\beta=0.055$, $p<0.05$), durability ($\beta=0.137$, $p<0.05$) and class ($\beta=0.428$, $p<0.05$) of Smartphones had an individual significant influence on purchase decision of Smartphones.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary

This study examined the role of online advertising in consumers' perception and purchase decision of Smartphones. This study adopted the multi-stage sampling technique to select 808 Lagos State residents. Four research assistants including the researcher administered copies of the questionnaire. Six hundred and fifty copies were retrieved and validated for analysis, making up 79.7 percent response rate.

Online advertising have become widespread in many societies, the study focused on the perception of importance attached to Smartphones brands in terms of being a status uplifting device as argued by Kotler and Armstrong (2010) leads to purchase decision. The issue of perception of quality, durability, price and features also complicate the reality of consumer perception and purchase decision of Smartphones as consumers would have to be aware of a particular Smartphone brand in this case through online advertisements through email, mobile, search engine and social media, thereafter consumers would use their perception capabilities in order to consider, evaluate and then finally purchase Smartphone brands that meet their consumers' specifications.

The literature identified types of advertising and narrows down to conceptualization of online advertising and specifically on Smartphone advertising. The study was anchored Gibson's theory of direct perception, and AIDA model. The research design adopted was the survey research design while the sampling technique adopted for the selection of respondents was the multi-stage sampling technique. Statistical Product and Service Solution, Version 21 was used to analyze the data.

The study revealed that Lagos State residents were generally averagely exposed to online Smartphone advertising to a low extent (Mean= 3.26, SD=1.40). However, they were exposed to social media advertising to a great extent (Mean= 3.67, SD=1.25), while the study participants had been averagely exposed to mobile advertising of Smartphones (Mean= 3.21, SD=1.42) and e-mail advertising of Smartphones to a low extent (Mean=2.77, SD=1.49). Consumers were more aware of *iPhone* (59.1%), *Samsung* (48.6%), *HTC*

(46.8%) and *Techno* (46.3%) brands of Smartphones. Lagos State residents generally paid attention to online advertisements to a low extent (Mean=3.24, SD=1.37), they however paid more attention to graphic quality (Mean=3.97, SD=1.32) and pictures displayed (Mean=3.51, SD=1.40) to a great extent, while Lagos State residents paid attention to a low extent to wordings and lettering style (Mean=3.30, SD=1.30) and pop up messages of online advertisements (Mean=2.98, SD=1.50). Lagos State residents generally had a positive perception of Smartphones (Mean= 4.01, SD=1.02). Lagos State residents had the highest perception of Smartphone *Feature* (Mean= 4.29, SD=0.91), followed by *Durability* (Mean= 4.15, SD=0.99), *Class* (Mean= 4.01, SD=1.10), *Quality* (Mean= 3.75, SD=1.07) and *Price* (Mean= 3.69, SD=1.15). Finally, Lagos State residents perceived a relationship between purchase decision and perception of Smartphone advertised online (Mean= 3.68, SD=1.32)

5.2 Conclusion

Online advertising is important especially in the 21st century with the widespread adoption of telecommunication devices such as Smartphones. Smartphones are digital devices that can enhance accurate targeting of consumers through social media, mobile, search engine and email advertising. This forms an inevitable gateway for the basis of consumers' perception of Smartphones advertised online in terms of features, durability, quality class and price; a positive perception thereafter inadvertently leads to consumer purchase decision of Smartphones. In line with what was revealed in the finding of this research work, it is obvious that the advertisements of smartphones online is a propelling factor that positively influences the perception and purchase decision of consumers. It is therefore strategic for Smartphone manufacturers, vendors and marketers to adopt online advertising through social media, search engine, mobile and email advertising in order to increase consumers' positive perception of Smartphone features, durability, quality and price.

In line with the first objective of this study in measuring the consumers' level of exposure to online advertisements, the respondents are exposed to online advertising to a great extent, they are also aware of Smartphone brands advertised online, although they do not pay much attention to the wordings of online Smartphone advertisements, its graphics attracts them. The respondents have a positive perception of Smartphone features as they relate with its functionality and its ability to perform consumer specific tasks. Finally, the last objective of

this study as regards finding out if there is an existing relationship between consumers' perception and purchase decision of smartphones reveals that there is a perceived relationship by the respondents about the perception and purchase decision of Smartphones. This is evident because the study revealed that the perception of consumers as a result of being exposed to online advertisements leads to the eventual purchase of smartphones. It is therefore strategic for Smartphone manufacturers, vendors and marketers to identify online platforms that enhance user interactivity with the potential for consumer online Smartphone advertisement customized exposure.

5.3 Recommendations

This study recommends to Smartphone manufacturers, marketers, vendors and about the appropriate online advertising platform for Smartphones. The recommendations are as follows:

5.3.1 Smartphone Manufacturers, Marketers and Vendors

The study revealed that Lagos State residents were more aware of online advertisements of *Iphone, Samsung, HTC* and *Techno* than other brands of Smartphones such as *Sony, Philips,* and *Alcatel*. The reason that is associated with this is the Smartphone manufacturers' strategic plan to adopt online advertising for their brands or not to. It is therefore necessary for Smartphone manufacturers to leverage online platforms such as social media and search engine advertising because they presently offer the best capabilities for customizing interactive and user specific Smartphone advertisements without being perceived as unsolicited. However, Smartphone manufacturer should not also ignore mobile and email advertising. In addition, Smartphone manufacturers need to maintain the positive perception of Smartphones from the perspective of features, durability, quality, class and price. This means that consumers need to continue to perceive Smartphones to be useful for completing various tasks, while being seen as durable, with the right quality and have the ability to increase the social class of owners at the right price so as to bring about a positive purchase decision of consumers. Smartphone marketers and vendors also need to adopt online platforms that have the capability of user specific customizable advertising experience. This will ensure that consumers who receive Smartphone advertisements most likely want to

thereby increasing the chance of paying attention to such advertisement, hence enhancing Smartphone brand awareness, perception and purchase decision.

5.3.2 Online Advertising Platforms for Smartphones

The adoption of online advertising platforms enhances the attention of consumers towards Smartphone advertisements, positive perception building and purchase decision. This is clearly evident in the value of the mean deviation and standard deviation of the respondents that are attracted by online advertising. This suggests that online platforms such as social media, search engines and mobile advertising through in *app* advertisements have the most potential for online Smartphone advertising.

5.4 Contribution to Knowledge

This study examined the role of online advertising in consumers' perception and purchase decision of Smartphones. The contribution to knowledge is in following areas, concept, empirical, theory and practice.

In the area of concept, this study adopted an expanded approach towards examining the role of online advertising in consumers' perception and purchase decision of Smartphones. It included online advertising such as social media, search engine, mobile and email showing how they expose consumers to Smartphone advertisements, in order to enhance Smartphone perception for purchase decision. It was revealed that the type of online advertising platform matters in terms of consumer customization for easy and strategic targeting by Smartphone manufacturers, marketers and vendors. From indications in the study, it is obvious that positive perception of smartphones brands advertised online can positively influence the purchase decision of consumers.

The empirical contribution of this work is centered on the fact that Online Smartphone advertising platforms in terms of social media, search engine, mobile and email with consumers' perception from the perspective of Smartphone feature, durability, quality, class and price was adopted for the first time as necessary factors that need to be considered to ensure a positive purchase decision of Smartphones.

In contributing to the theoretical body of knowledge, this study reveals that Smartphone manufacturer, marketers and vendors can improve consumers' perception of Smartphones if they adopt the appropriate online advertising platform and measures to target consumers. Consequently, consumers' perception will be improved positively, thereby ensuring consumer attention to Smartphone advertisements, which leads to purchase decision of Smartphones. This study has consequently contributed to the application of Gibson's theory of direct perception, and AIDA model.

In the area of practice, Smartphone manufacturers, marketers and vendors have been given appropriate guidance about consumers' attention to online advertisements, appropriate online Smartphone advertisement platform in order to ensure that consumers' perception of Smartphones remain positive, thereby leading to purchase decision of Smartphones. This is however imperative in line with the fact that active online presence by smartphone consumers will help to retain the attention of consumers' smartphone brands thereby leading to the eventual purchase of their most preferred brand when they need it.

In contributing to policy making decisions, this study has developed a blueprint upon which policy makers in the field of advertising may build their marketing communication programmes to ensure that perception of Smartphone brands is positive in order to bring about purchase decision.

5.5 Limitations of the Study

This study was majorly focused on just two local government areas in Lagos. This means that there was a limitation to covering other local government areas within Lagos state due to the nature and scope of this particular research work. However, if more than two locations were considered, a different result may have been gotten.

Moreover, few challenges were being encountered by the researcher in the course of carrying out the entire research exercise. Data gathering was fatiguing in nature due to the reason that there were series of formal protocols to be observed in accordance to the official policy of the local government areas which were being focused on in Lagos state for the purpose of this study.

However in the process of getting some of the questionnaires to be distributed within Ikeja local government area of Lagos state, some of the respondents were reluctant to the idea of getting the questionnaires filled. The researcher had to continually assure and convince the respondents about the confidential nature of the questionnaire despite the rowdy atmosphere of Ikeja and the harsh weather condition within the period when the questionnaire was administered.

5.6 Suggestion for Further Studies

Diverse regional locations and Local government areas within the geographical sphere of Nigeria can be studied by future researcher depending on the advantage of the time and period for the researchers. This will create a wider perspective to the perception and purchase decision of smartphone consumers who have a maximum level of exposure to online advertisement.

Further studies should be carried out to ascertain how email advertising of Smartphones could be customized to suit consumer advertising preferences. In addition, studies should be conducted on mobile advertising from the perspective of software applications in advertising. This is necessary because many Smartphone applications have in-built advertising capabilities, this also needs to be studied more so as to ascertain its impact on Smartphone consumer perception and purchase decision. The influence of online testimonials on consumers' awareness of smartphone brands can also be studied by future researchers.

REFERENCES

- Adekoya, O. A. (2011). The impact of advertising on sales volume of a product: *A case study of Starcomms Plc, Nigeria* A Bachelors Thesis, HAMK University of Applied Sciences.
Retrieved from http://www.theseus.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/34928/Adekoya_Olusa.pdf
- Adelabu, O. (2015). Social Media, Advertising messages and the youth: Any influence? *New Media and Mass Communication*, 39, 19. Retrieved from <http://www.iiste.org/Journals/index.php/NMMC/article/download/24012/24582>
- Aggrawal, A. (2010). Impact of consumer perception on buying behavior in apparel retail sector, with special reference to selected Indian cities. A PhD Thesis, Padmashree Dr. D. Y. Patil University, Navi Mumba. Retrieved from <http://dypusm.com/pdf/thesis/AmitAggrawal-2010-Ph.D.pdf>
- Alkubise. (2012). How do online advertisement affect consumer purchase intention: Emperical evidence from a developing country. *European journal of business management*, 12(4), 208-21.
- Altena. (2012). How a Smartphone can benefit your health. Retrieved from <http://www.acsm.org/public-information/articles/2012/02/02/how-a-smartphone-can-benefit-your-health>
- Alves, T. O. (2014). Assessing the relative performance of online advertising media. A Masters Thesis, Católica-Lisbon School of Business & Economics. Retrieved from <http://repositorio.ucp.pt/bitstream/10400.14/15268/1/Tom%C3%A1s%20Alves%20-%20Thesis.pdf>
- Bakshi & Gupta. (2013). Onlne Advertising and Its Impact on Consumer Buying Behavior. *International Journal of Research in Finance and Marketing*, 3(1), 21-30
- Baldauf, A, Cravens, K. S., & Binder, G. (2003). Performance consequences of brand equity management: evidence from organizations in the value chain. *Journal of Product & Brand Management*, 12(4), 220-236
- Bednall, S., & Kanuk, W. (1997). *Consumer Behaviour*. Australia: Prentice Hall
- Belch, G. E., & Belch, M. A. (2008). *Advertising and Promotion: An Integrated Marketing Communication Perspective*. (6th ed.). New York: Irwin
- Beverland, M. (2005). Brand management and the challenge of authenticity. *Journal of Product & Brand Management*, 14(7), 460-461
- Blackwell, R. D., Miniard, P. W., & Engel, J. F. (2001). *Consumer Behaviour*. Orlando: Harcourt College Publishers
- Blank (2013) *Consumer perception Theory*: Retrieved from <http://smallbusiness.chron.com/consumer-perception-theory-40176.html>

- Boadu, V. (2012). *A Study to indicate Factors influencing the buying Behaviour of Cigarette Smokers* (Bachelor Thesis, University of Applied Sciences.). Retrieved from https://monami.hs-mittweida.de/frontdoor/deliver/index/docId/2551/file/Bachelor_Thesis_2012.pdf
- Bray, J. (n.d). *Consumer Behaviour Theory: Approaches and Models*. Retrieved from http://eprints.bournemouth.ac.uk/10107/1/Consumer_Behaviour_Theory__Approaches_%26_Models.pdf
- Brierley, S. (2002). *The Advertising Handbook*. London: Routledge.
- Businessstopia (2016). AIDA model. Retrieved from <https://www.businessstopia.net/communication/aida=model>
- Butterfield, L. (1997). *Excellence in advertising, The IPA guide to best practice*. Oxford: British Library Cataloguing.
- CCS Insight. (2014). Global smartphone market analysis and outlook: Disruption in a changing market. Retrieved from <http://www.lenovo.com/transactions/pdf/CCS-Insight-Smartphone-Market-Analysis-Full-Report-07-2014.pdf>
- Cheng, L. W. (2011). *Econometrics*. Princeton University Press. Entry, its deterrence, and its accommodation: A study of the U. S. photographic film industry. *Rand Journal of Economics*, 27(3), 452-478.
- Christopher, A., John, S. F., & Sudhahar, C. (2014). Influence of peer in purchase decision making of smart phone: A study conducted in Coimbatore. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 4(8), 1-7. Retrieved from <http://www.ijsrp.org/research-paper-0814/ijsrp-p3261.pdf>
- Court, D. E., Mulder D., & Vetvik, O. J. (2009). The consumer decision journey. *McKinsey Quarterly*. Retrieved from http://www.mckinsey.com/insights/marketing_sales/the_consumer_decision_journey.
- Creswell, J. W. (2009). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (3 ed.). Los Angeles: Sage. Retrieved from <https://vivauniversity.files.wordpress.com/2014/02/creswell-2008-research-design-qualitative-quantitative-and-mixed-methods-approaches.pdf>
- Delong, M., Bao, M., Wu, J., Chao, H., & Li, M. (2004). Perception of U.S. branded apparel in Shanghai. *Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management*, 8(2), 141-153.
- Démuth, A. (2013). *Perception theories*. Retrieved from [http://fff.truni.sk/userdata/ebooks/demuthe_perception_theories%20\(1.1\).pdf](http://fff.truni.sk/userdata/ebooks/demuthe_perception_theories%20(1.1).pdf)
- Ducoffe, R. H. (1996). Advertising value and advertising on the web. *Journal of Advertising Research*, 36, 21-35.
- Dwarika, P. & Gandhi, A. V. (2007). *Managing retailing: Lost forever in a shopping mall*. Oxford: University Press.

- Dziri, R. (2011). *Avoiding strategic drifts in a hypercompetitive market: Analysis of Nokia's position in the mobile phone industry and suggestions*. A Masters Thesis, Berlin School of Economics and Law). Retrieved from <https://opus4.kobv.de/opus4-hwr/frontdoor/deliver/index/docId/39/file/Dziri,Ramzi.pdf>
- Dzisah, W. E., & Ocloo, C. E. (2013). Celebrity endorsement and consumer buying behaviour: Enhancing the promotion function of marketing in the Central Business Area of Accra, Ghana. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 5(25). Retrieved from <http://iiste.org/Journals/index.php/EJBM/article/viewFile/8056/8545>
- Gilbert, D. (2013). *Samsung's \$14bn is 'biggest marketing budget in history*. Retrieved from <http://www.ibtimes.co.uk/samsung-14bn-marketing-budget-biggest-history-525979>
- Grover, R., & Vriens, M. (2006). *The handbook of marketing research*. Thousand Oaks: Sage Publication Ltd.
- Hackley, C. (2005). *Advertising and promotion: Communicating brands*. London SAGE,
- Heinonen, T., & Rozenveld, M. (2013). *Challenges facing the advertising world in the digital era: A comparison between Dutch and Swedish advertising agencies*. (Masters Thesis). Retrieved from <http://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:635061/FULLTEXT01.pdf>
- Jamalzadeh, Behravan & Masoudi. (2012). An empirical study of email-based advertisement and its influence on consumers' attitude. *International Review of Management and Marketing* 2(3), 1-9.
- James, D. (2005). Guilty through association: Brand association transfer to brand alliances. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 22(1), 12-24.
- Jordão, S. (2010). Developing a multidimensional, equal-weighted scale of brand equity for the smartphone segment. A Masters Thesis, European School of Management and Technology, Berlin. Retrieved from http://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=1881672
- Kazmi, S. Q (2012). Consumer perception and buying decisions (The Pasta Study). *International Journal of Advancements in Research & Technology*, 1(6). Retrieved from http://www.ijoart.org/docs/Consumer_Perception_and_Buying_Decisions.pdf
- Kantar World Panel (2014). Mobile trends that matter tomorrow: An insight report by Kantar world panel tech. Retrieved from http://www.kantarworldpanel.com/dwl.php?sn=news_downloads&id=431
- Keller, K. L. (2003). Brand synthesis: The multidimensionality of brand knowledge. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 29, 595-600.
- Khanuja, A. S. (2013). Consumer perception towards smartphones (A Masters Thesis, ICFAI Business School, Hyderabad). Retrieved from http://s3.amazonaws.com/academia.edu.documents/33103551/Consumer_Perception_Towards_Smartphones.docx?AWSAccessKeyId=AKIAJ56TQJRTWSMTNPEA&Expires=1471610354&Signature=MJF

QOHn7XxtI6folFSldkJOI6rc%3D&response content disposition=attachment%3B%20filename%3DConsumer_Perception_Towards_Smartphones.docx

- Kotler, & Armstrong (2010). *Principles of marketing*. 3rd edition, Pearson Education.
- Kotler, P. (2000). *Marketing Management*. New Jersey: Prentice Hall International
- Kumar, A. K. (2011). Term paper: Online advertisement,. Hochschule Furtwangen University. Retrieved from <http://webuser.hs-furtwangen.de/~heindI/ebte-08ss-Online Advertisement-Kumar.pdf>
- Lay-Yee, K. L., Han, K. S., & Yin-Fah, B. C. (2013). Factors affecting smartphone purchase decision among Malaysian generation Y. *International Journal of Asian Social Science*, 3(12), 2426-2440. Retrieved from [http://www.aessweb.com/pdf-files/ijass%203\(12\)-2426-2440.pdf](http://www.aessweb.com/pdf-files/ijass%203(12)-2426-2440.pdf)
- LearnMarketing.net. (2015). Hierarchy of effects model. Retrieved from http://www.learnmarketing.net/hierarchy_of_effect_smodel.html
- Leibel, M. (2014). Samsung leads U.S. ad spending for smartphones, but Apple and others aren't far behind. Retrieved from <http://venturebeat.com/2014/04/08/samsung-leads-us-ad-spending-but-apple-and-others-are-making-it-close/>
- Lightcap, B. C., & Peek, W. A. (2012). The effects of digital media on advertising markets. (Bachelors Thesis, Duke University Durham, North Carolina). Retrieved from https://econ.duke.edu/uploads/media_items/lightcap-peek-thesis-dje-final.original.pdf
- Macdonald, E. K., & Sharp, B. M., (2000). Brand awareness effects on consumer decision making for a common, repeat purchase product: A replication. *Journal of Business Research*, 5-1.
- Macey, F. (1900). The Bissell Prize Advertisement Contest, Hardware, p. 44.
- Malviya, S., Saluja, M. S, & Thakur, A. S. (2013). A study on the factors influencing consumer's purchase decision towards smartphones in Indore. *International Journal of Advance Research in Computer Science and Management Studies*, 1(6), 14-21. Retrieved from <http://www.ijarcsms.com/docs/paper/volume1/issue6/v1i6-0003.pdf>
- McCoy, S., Everard, A., Galletta, D., & Polak, P. (2004) A study of the effects of online advertising: A focus on op-Up and In-Line ads *Proceedings of the Third Annual Workshop on HCI Research in MIS, Washington, D.C., December 10-11*. Retrieved from <http://interruptions.net/literature/McCoy-HCIRMIS04.pdf>.
- Miller, Chris (2004), *Blood on My Briefcase: 30 Years in the Advertising Wars* (USA: Xlibris Corporation).
- Mohan, A. (2014). Consumer behaviour towards smartphone industry In Indian market A Masters Thesis, Dublin Business School). Retrieved from http://esource.dbs.ie/bitstream/handle/10788/1812/mba_mohan_a_2014.pdf?sequence=1
- Morris, J., Marzano, M., Dandy, N., & O'Brien, L. (2012). Theories and models of behaviour and behaviour change. Retrieved from

[http://www.forestry.gov.uk/pdf/behaviour_review_theory.pdf/\\$FILE/behaviour_review_theory.pdf](http://www.forestry.gov.uk/pdf/behaviour_review_theory.pdf/$FILE/behaviour_review_theory.pdf)

- Muniz, A. M., & O'Guinn, T. C. (2001). Brand community. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 27(4). Retrieved from www.jstor.org/stable/10.1086/319618
- Nagarkoti, B. (2009). Factors influencing consumer behavior of smartphone users (A Bachelors Thesis, Arcada. Retrieve from http://theseus32.kk.lib.helsinki.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/70466/Nagarkoti_Bishal.pdf?sequence=1
- Nguy, K. (2000). Consumer perceptions of the internet as a product and service information source. A Bachelors Thesis, Edith Cowan University, Western Australia). Retrieved from http://ro.ecu.edu.au/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1148&context=theses_hons
- Nigerian Communications Commission. (2016). Subscriber statistics. Retrieved from http://ncc.gov.ng/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=125&Itemid=731
- Nwankwo, B. E., Aboh, J. U., Obi, T. C., Agu, S. A., & Sydney-Agbor, N. (2013). Influence of advertising appeals and personality on telecoms consumption preferences in Nigeria. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences* 3(9), 229-237. Retrieved from http://hrmars.com/hrmars_papers/Influence_of_Advertising_Appeals_and_Personality_on_Telecoms_Consumption_Preferences_in_Nigeria.pdf
- Osman, M. A., Talib A. Z., Sanusi, Z. A., Yen, S. T., & Alwi, A. S. (2012). A study of the trend of smartphone and its usage behavior in Malaysia. *International Journal on New Computer Architectures and Their Applications*, 2(1), 275-286. Retrieved from http://sdiwc.us/digitlib/journal_paper.php?paper=00000160.pdf
- Papadopoulos, S. (2009). Key success factors in internet advertising: With emphasis on Online user Activity and the social context. A Masters Thesis, Blekinge Institute of Technology. Retrieved from <http://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:830978/FULLTEXT01.pdf>
- Patel, R. K. (2014). A Study on consumer behavior and opportunities for Nokia smartphones in India. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal GIIRJ*, 2(1), 65-97. Retrieved from <http://internationaljournals.co.in/pdf/giirj/2014/january/6.pdf>
- Petrauskaite, E. (2014). Effect of brand image on consumer purchase behaviour: International footwear market comparison. A Masters Thesis, Aalborg University). Retrieved from http://projekter.aau.dk/projekter/files/198320070/Master_Thesis_Egle_Petrauskaite.pdf
- Randall, G. (2000). *Branding – A practical guide to planning your strategy*, (2nd edition), England

- Robens, C. (2007). *Consumer perceptions on the incorporation of established brands: The acquisition of Body Shop by L'Oréal* (Masters Thesis, N/A). Retrieved from <http://www.diva-portal.se/smash/get/diva2:119755/FULLTEXT01.pdf>
- Saleem. (2013). Effective advertising and its influence on consumer buying behavior. *European journal of business management*. 3(3), 55-6
- Schiffman, B., & Kanuk, W. (1997). *Consumer Behaviour*. Australia: Prentice Hall.
- Shareef, M. A., Kumar, U., and Kumar, V. (2008). Role of Different Electronic-Commerce (EC) Quality Factors on Purchase Decision: A Developing Country Perspective. *Journal of Electronic Commerce Research*, 9(2), 92-113. Retrieved from <http://web.csulb.edu/journals/jecr/issues/20082/paper2.pdf>
- Shimp, T. (2010). Processes, Brand Equity, and Marcon's Role in Introducing New Brands. In: Roche, M. *Advertising, Promotion, and Other Aspects of Integrated Marketing Communications*. 37-38.
- Shin, S., Lee, W. J. & Odom, D. (2014). A Comparative Study Of Smartphone User's Perception And Preference Towards Mobile Payment Methods In The U.S. And Korea. *The Journal of Applied Business Research*, 30 (5),1365-1375. Retrieved from <http://cluteinstitute.com/ojs/index.php/JABR/article/download/8793/8765>
- Soo, J.G. (2015). *Strategic analysis of Samsung's smartphone product portfolio: Countering the challenge from Chinese competitors* (Masters Thesis, Sungkyunkwan University). Retrieved from <https://dspace.mit.edu/bitstream/handle/1721.1/99007/921185669-MIT.pdf?sequence=1>
- Strong, P. (1925a). *The Psychology of Selling and Advertising*. New York: McCraw-Hill
- Tavor, T. (2011). Online Advertising Development And Their Economic Effectiveness. *Australian Journal of Business and Management Research*, 1(6)121-133. Retrieved from http://www.ajbmr.com/articlepdf/AJBMR_16_15_1.pdf
- Thomas, Altena. (2012). How a Smartphone can benefit your health. Retrieved from <http://www.acsm.org/public-information/articles/2012/02/02/how-a-smartphone-can-benefit-your-health>
- Todi, M. (2008). *Advertising on Social Networking Websites*. (Masters Thesis, University of Pennsylvania, Pennsylvania). Retrieved from http://repository.upenn.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1054&context=wharton_research_scholars
- Tung, W. C (2003). *A Customer Perception and Satisfaction Survey for a Chinese Buffet* (Masters thesis, University of Wisconsin-Stout, Menomonie). Retrieved from <http://www2.uwstout.edu/content/lib/thesis/2003/2003tungw.pdf>
- Vaughan, P. (2012). *An introduction to inbound marketing analytics*. Retrieved from <http://www.emarkable.ie/training/strategy%20marketing/An-Introduction-to-Inbound-Marketing-Analytics.pdf>

- Vikström, H., & Zheng, C. (2013). Branding through mobile applications: A case study of Swedish campaign applications (Masters Thesis, KTH Industrial Engineering and Management Industrial Management Stockholm, Sweden). Retrieved from <http://www.diva-portal.se/smash/get/diva2:632741/FULLTEXT01.pdf>
- Wollenberg, A. & Thuong, T.T (2014) Consumer Behaviour in the Smartphone Market in Vietnam *International Journal of Innovation, Management and Technology*, 5(6) 412-415. Retrieved from <http://www.ijimt.org/papers/550-E002.pdf>
- Zipporah, M. M. & Mberia, H. K. (2014). The Effects OF Celebrity Endorsement in Advertisements, *International Journal of Academic Research in Economics and Management Sciences*, 3(5). Retrieved from http://hrmars.com/hrmars_papers/The_Effects_OF_Celebrity_Endorsement_in_Advertisements.pdf

QUESTIONNAIRE

Department of Mass Communication,
Babcock University,
Ilishan Remo,
Ogun State.

Dear sir/ma,

I am a post graduate student in the Department of Mass Communication, Babcock University, conducting a study examining the role of online advertising in consumers' perception and purchase decision of smartphones. I hereby seek your answers to the questionnaire items; you are assured that all information given shall be kept confidential and shall only be used for the purpose of this study.

Thanks.

Yours faithfully,

Shofodurin Adetayo

Section A: General Details

In this section, you are required to select your demographic details and to give general details on smartphones.

Please tick appropriately.

1. Gender (a) Male (b) Female
2. Age (a) 15-24 (b) 24-30 (c) 31-40 (d) 41-50 (e) 51 and above (f) Others please specify _____
3. Do you have a smartphone? (a) Yes (b) No
4. For how long have you been using a smartphone?
 - (a) Less than 1 year
 - (b) 1 year - 5 years
 - (c) 6 years - 10 years
 - (d) More than 10 years

5. Which of the following brands of smartphones do you use presently?

- (a) Alcatel [] (b) Gionee []
- (c) HTC [] (d) Infinix []
- (e) iPhone [] (f) itel []
- (g) Lenovo [] (h) LG []
- (i) Nokia [] (j) Philips []
- (k) Samsung [] (l) Sony []
- (m) Techno [] (n) Blackberry []

Others, please specify _____

Section B: Consumers’ Exposure, awareness and attention to Online Advertisements

In this section, you are needed to indicate the type of advertisement(s) you see online, the medium, your level of exposure, awareness and attention

Please indicate the strength of your response in the following order (To a Great Extent= TGEX, Great Extent= GEX, Little Extent = LEX, Very Little Extent = VLEX, Not at all = NT)

Exposure and awareness to online advertisements	TGEX	GEX	LEX	VLEX	NT
6. I am aware of online advertisements					
7. Online advertisements are attractive					
8. I see online advertisements regularly					
9. I spend much time concentrating on online advertisements					
10. I spend less time concentrating on online advertisements					

Please indicate the strength of your response in the following order (To a Great Extent= TGEX, Great Extent= GEX, Little Extent = LEX, Very Little Extent = VLEX, Not at all = NT)

Attention towards perception	TGEX	GEX	LEX	VLEX	NT
11. Graphics quality of online advertisements attract me					
12. Pictures displayed via online advertisements attract me					
13. Wordings and lettering style of online advertisements attract me					
14. Pop up messages of online advertisements attract me					
15. Advertisements sent to my mail attracts me					

E-mail Advertising

16. I have an e-mail address (a) Yes [] (b) No []

Please indicate the strength of your response in the following order (To a Great Extent= TGEX, Great Extent= GEX, Little Extent = LEX, Very Little Extent = VLEX, Not at all = NT)

E-Mail Advertising	TGEX	GEX	LEX	VLEX	NT
17. I receive e-mails					
18. Smartphone advertisements are displayed in the e-mail window					
19. Pop-up smartphone advertisements are sent to e-mail windows					
20. Competing brands of smartphone advertisements are presented in e-mail windows					
21. Unsolicited or unwanted e-mail smartphone advertisements are received					

Search Engine Advertising

Please indicate the strength of your response in the following order (To a Great Extent= TGEX, Great Extent= GEX, Little Extent = LEX, Very Little Extent = VLEX, Not at all = NT)

Search Engine Advertising	TGEX	GEX	LEX	VLEX	NT
22. I use search engines (e.g. Google, Bing, Yahoo, Ask.com)					
23. I search for smartphones on search engines					
24. Smartphone results on search engines appear from advertisers and marketers					
25. Competing brands of smartphone advertisements are seen on search engine results					

Mobile Advertising

Please indicate the strength of your response in the following order (To a Great Extent= TGEX, Great Extent= GEX, Little Extent = LEX, Very Little Extent = VLEX, Not at all = NT)

Mobile Advertising	TGEX	GEX	LEX	VLEX	NT
26. Smartphone advertisements are sent through mobile devices					
27. Smartphone advertisements are received on phone applications (Apps)					
28. Competing brands of smartphone advertisements are seen on phone applications (Apps)					
29. Smartphone advertisements are received on SMS					
30. Competing brands of smartphone advertisements are sent through SMS					

Social Media Advertising

Please indicate the strength of your response in the following order (To a Great Extent= TGEX, Great Extent= GEX, Little Extent = LEX, Very Little Extent = VLEX, Not at all = NT)

31. I have social a media account(s) (a) Yes [] (b) No []

Social Media Advertising	TGEX	GEX	LEX	VLEX	NT
32. Smartphone advertisements are received on the social media					
33. Competing brands of smartphone advertisements are seen on the social media					

Section C: Consumer Smartphone Brand Awareness

In this section, please indicate the Smartphone brands you have heard about

34. Which of the following brands of Smartphones have you seen online (Mobile, Social media, Email, Internet) before?

(b) Alcatel [] (b) Gionee [] (c) HTC [] (d) Infinix []

(e) iPhone [] (f) itel [] (g) Lenovo [] (h) LG []

(i) Nokia [] (j) Philips [] (k) Samsung [] (l) Sony []

(m) Techno [] (n) Blackberry []

Others, please specify _____

Section D: Consumer Perception of Smartphone Advertised Online

In this section, please indicate your perception of the Smartphone brands advertised online.

Please indicate the strength of your response in the following order (Strongly Agree= SA, Agree = A, Strongly Disagree= SD, Disagree = D, Undecided = U)

Price	SA	A	SD	D	U
35. Smartphone price does not matter					
36. Smartphone price means quality					
37. Expensive Smartphones are original products					
38. Non-expensive Smartphones are durable					
39. Expensive Smartphone offer more features than non-expensive ones					
40. Expensive Smartphones are symbol of class in the society					
41. Non- expensive Smartphones befits high class gatherings					

Please indicate the strength of your response in the following order (Strongly Agree= SA, Agree = A, Strongly Disagree= SD, Disagree = D, Undecided = U)

Features	SA	A	SD	D	U
42. Smartphones features enhance inter and intra personal communication					
43. E-mail management are better with Smartphones					
44. Downloading and uploading of files are efficient on Smartphones					
45. Smartphones are used for management of personal activities					
46. Smartphones make sharing of information and resources easier					
47. Smartphone applications are useful					
48. Feature for playing music on Smartphones is needed					
49. Features for playing games on Smartphones is needed					
50. I like Smartphones with big screens					
51. I like Smartphones with buttons					
52. I like Smartphones that are colourful					

Please indicate the strength of your response in the following order (Strongly Agree= SA, Agree = A, Strongly Disagree= SD, Disagree = D, Undecided = U)

Quality	SA	A	SD	D	U
53. Quality is reflected in the beauty of the Smartphone					
54. Quality is reflected in the weight of the Smartphone					
55. Smartphone quality is reliable					
56. Smartphone quality can be determined by the performance of manufacturers' past products					
57. Smartphone quality is determined by manufacturers' warranty					
58. Smartphone quality is determined by details presented in advertisements					

Please indicate the strength of your response in the following order (Strongly Agree= SA, Agree = A, Strongly Disagree= SD, Disagree = D, Undecided = U)

Durability	SA	A	SD	D	U
59. Smartphones are changed because they are not durable					
60. Smartphones that last 1 year are not durable					
61. Smartphones that last 2 years are not durable					
62. Smartphones that last longer than 3 years are necessarily not durable					
63. Smartphone screens are not strong					
64. Manufacturers deliberately make non-durable smartphones					

Please indicate the strength of your response in the following order (Strongly Agree= SA, Agree = A, Strongly Disagree= SD, Disagree = D, Undecided = U)

Class	SA	A	SD	D	U
65. Luxury fashion Smartphones are the true definition of Smartphones					
66. Smartphones can make you important among your peers					
67. A rare luxurious Smartphone can make someone unique					
68. The type of Smartphone someone uses can give someone respect					

Section E: Consumer Purchase Decision of Smartphones Advertised Online

Please indicate the strength of your response in the following order (Strongly Agree= SA, Agree = A, Strongly Disagree= SD, Disagree = D, Undecided = U)

Consumer Purchase Decision	SA	A	SD	D	U
69. Smartphones advertised online increases awareness of Smartphone brands					
70. More information is sought on Smartphones advertised online					
71. Advertising Smartphones online helps consumer evaluation					
72. Smartphones advertised online are considered by consumers					
73. Consumers purchase Smartphones advertised online					

Section F: Relationship between perception and Purchase Decision of Smartphones Advertised Online

Please indicate the strength of your response in the following order (Strongly Agree= SA, Agree = A, Strongly Disagree= SD, Disagree = D, Undecided = U)

Relationship between perception Purchase Decision	SA	A	SD	D	U
74. Smartphone(s) purchased by me is as a result of its seen advertisements online					
75. Price of advertised Smartphones Online determines my purchase decision					
76. Features of advertised Smartphones determines my purchase decision					
77. Quality of advertised Smartphones Online determines my purchase decision					
78. Durability of advertised Smartphones Online determines my purchase decision					
79. Class of advertised Smartphones Online determines my purchase decision					